

Deliverable

Project Acronym:	VRTogether
Grant Agreement number:	762111
Project Title:	<i>An end-to-end system for the production and delivery of photorealistic social immersive virtual reality experiences</i>

D5.2 - Market analysis report

Revision: 2.4

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Delivery date: M32 (May 2020)

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 762111		
Dissemination Level		
P	Public	x
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

Abstract: This deliverable describes the status of the market at April 2020 for audio-visual immersive products, with particular emphasis in social VR platforms and related technologies, and provides a set of recommendations towards an improved exploitation plan of the project results.

REVISION HISTORY

Revision	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
0.1	15 May 19	Loïc Landais	Viaccess-Orca	First Draft
0.11	21 June 19	Tom De Koninck	TNO	Update of standardization section
0.2	16 July 19	Loïc Landais	Viaccess-Orca	Second Draft
0.25	8 August 19	Marc BreLOT	MSE	Internal first review
0.3	29 August 19	Pascal Perrot	Viaccess-Orca	Modifications based on review's feedback
1.0	24 September 19	Pascal Perrot	Viaccess-Orca	Final version
1.5	28 February	Pascal Perrot	Viaccess-Orca	Update of Market status Feb 2020
2.0	March	Pascal Perrot	Viaccess-Orca	New section Identified Stakeholders
2.1	April	Pascal Perrot	Viaccess-Orca	Extension of section 3
2.4	May	Pascal Perrot	Viaccess-Orca	Update of Market Overview, conclusion

Disclaimer

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Statement of originality:

This document contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
AR/VR/MR	Augmented Reality / Virtual Reality / Mixed Reality
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Consumer
B2B2C	Business to Business to Consumer
CAD	Computer-Aided Drawing
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
DoF	Degrees of Freedom
FoV	Field of View
GPU	Graphic Processing Unit
HMD	Head Mounted Displays
MMO	Massively Multiplayer Online
Mo-Cap	Motion Capture
MPEG	Moving Picture Experts Group
ODMs	Original Design Manufacturing
OEMs	Original Equipment Manufacturing
RGB-D	Red Green Blue - Depth
RPG	Role Playing Games
XR	Extended Reality

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Purpose of this document

The objective of this document is to analyse the current status of the market as of April 2020 and the forecasted future market opportunities for immersive audio-visual products by:

- Shedding light on changing behaviours and associated expectations in audio-visual consumption.
- Assessing the market potential of the solutions developed within VRTogether both in terms of enhancing existing formats and in creating new types of content.
- Identify target users (end-users) and sales channels (B2B,B2C,B2G...) of the solution and how they could be successfully exploited.

1.2. Status and final scope of this document

The present document will be alive during the whole project period, that is, during the 3 iterations of the project. Three different versions will be formally submitted to the European Community and uploaded on the project website.

The first version focused on providing an in-depth overview of the immersive audio-visual market.

At present, this is the second version of the document and aims to provide an update on some of the topics stated in the first version. Additionally, the document will also focus on new market opportunities like Augmented Reality (AR).

A third version to be presented in the following months, will focus on the presentation of the VRTogether's solution, the enabled use cases and on a set of recommendations to ensure a successful launch on the market. The document will particularly highlight:

- How the solution could or should be transformed into a viable product (value proposition, functional set-up, value network and financial model).
- The conditions for a successful exploitation of the proposed solution and the associated optimal go-to-market strategy.

1.3. Relation with other VRTogether activities

This document is framed in Work Package 5, one of the objectives of which is to maximize the impact of the VRTogether platform on the immersive technology market and research domain. The results of the project are expected to have a significant impact on the audio-visual market. This WP will:

- Determine overall conditions for successful exploitation of the proposed solutions, such as standardization, additional stakeholder involvement, etc.
- Identify optimal go-to-market strategies of products using VRTogether technologies. The project should take into account specific requirements of each of the stakeholders and be translated into feasible and viable exploitation plans.
- Organize maximal visibility for the proposed solutions by attending major relevant events and setting up direct contacts with potential customers.
- Implement a communication strategy aligned with the exploitation strategies of the consortium partners.

2. VR MARKET OVERVIEW

2.1. VR/AR revenue forecasts

As of January 2019, estimates by SuperData suggest that the consumer market for immersive technology will generate US\$10.6 billion dollars in revenue globally by 2019. The single largest segment of the market is Virtual Reality (VR) which will account for \$6.2 billion of the total, while Mobile Augmented Reality and Augmented/Mixed Reality headsets will bring in around \$4.7 billion combined.

Immersive technology seeks to simulate physical scenarios and environments for users, thereby leading to a broad range of expected uses from professional, training or entertainment applications.

The immersive technology market is forecasted to steadily grow to a \$34.1 billion market by 2023, driven by technological improvements and as the consumer electronic devices which enable the use of this technologies become increasingly available.

The forecasted estimates are underpinned by VRs explosive growth, expected to expand at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of +45.87% for 2018-2023 period. The drastic expansion is expected to result in a \$16.3 billion VR market by the end of the forecasted period. Concomitantly, the Mobile Augmented Reality and Augmented/Mixed Reality (AR/MR) headsets are forecasted to grow at an impressive CAGR of +51.97% and 101.24% respectively, to ultimately reach by 2023 the \$9.6 and \$8.2 billion market size milestone.

Figure 1 - Hardware and consumer software revenue: 2018-2022

Similar recent reports highlight the prosperity of the Virtual and Augmented Reality market. For instance, International Data Corporation (IDC)^{1,2} VR/AR 2020 Market Report estimates a

¹ International Data Corporation, 2019. Worldwide Augmented and Virtual Reality Spending Guide. November 2019. Available from: <https://www.idc.com/getdoc.jsp?containerId=prUS45679219>

worldwide spending as of \$18.8 billion in 2020, an increase of 78.5% over the \$10.5 billion IDC expected 2019 market size. What is more, IDC forecasts predicts a strong growth throughout 2019-2023 period, achieving a five-year CAGR of 77.0%.

Forecast augmented (AR) and virtual reality (VR) market size worldwide from 2016 to 2020 (in billion U.S. dollars)

Figure 2 - Forecast for AR/VR Market Size Worldwide, 2016-2020.

By region, IDC predicts China to concentrate the biggest AR/VR spending in 2020 at \$5.8 billion, closely followed by The United States with a total spending of \$5.1 billion. In third position, Europe is estimated to spend \$3.3 billion in 2020, followed by Japan with \$1.8 billion.

Augmented and virtual reality (AR/VR) forecast spending worldwide in 2020, by country (in billion U.S. dollars)

Figure 3 - AR/VR Forecast Spending in 2020, by Country.

² Statista, 2019. Forecast augmented (AR) and virtual reality (VR) market size worldwide from 2016 to 2020. Available from: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/591181/global-augmented-virtual-reality-market-size/>

2.2. AR/VR Market Applications

When it comes to AR/VR market applications to main independent, yet interconnected market applications segments can be identified: 1) consumer applications and 2) enterprise and public sector applications (often referred to as industrial).

According to IDC and as published by Statista³, consumer AR/VR segment will concentrate the bulk of the market, with a forecasted \$7 billion expenditure. In second place, Distribution and Services segment with a \$4.4 billions spending. Following, manufacture and resources, public sector and infrastructure segments with an estimated spending of \$3.6, \$2.6 and \$0.8 billions respectively. In terms of share, Consumer represents a 37,4% of the global AR/VR spending; distribution and services a 23,4%, Manufacturing and resources a 19,3% and Public Sector a 13,9%.

Augmented and virtual reality (AR/VR) forecast spending worldwide in 2020 (in billion U.S. dollars), by segment

Forecast share of augmented and virtual reality (AR/VR) spending worldwide in 2020, by segment

Figure 4 - AR/VR Spending Worldwide in 2020 by segment (Left); Forecast Share of AR/VR Spending Worldwide 2020 by segment (Right).

Focusing on the **VR Market applications segments**, IDC expects the largest consumer application of VR in 2019 to be **VR games** (\$4.0 billion). According to the market intelligence company, **video/feature viewing** and **AR games** are the next ones, with a forecast of respectively \$2.0 billion and \$616 million⁴.

A more recent forecast from IDC^{5,6} confirm such forecasted trends by analysing the expected investments by application segment. In fact, according to the data, the commercial use for AR/VR that is expected to represent the largest consumer use cases is VR Gaming, VR Video/feature viewing and AR gaming, with a combined investment of \$20.8 billion by 2023. The training application segment is expected to receive a large investment as well with \$8.5 billion. Last but not least, industrial maintenance and retail showcasing are also predicted to receive substantial investment by 2023, of \$4.3 and \$3.9 billion respectively.

³ Statista, 2019. Statista dossier about Virtual Reality (VR). Available from: <https://www.statista.com/study/29689/virtual-reality-vr-statista-dossier/>

⁴ IDC. Worldwide Spending on Augmented and Virtual Reality Expected to Surpass \$20 Billion in 2019, According to IDC [online]. (published December 6, 2018) Available on: <https://www.idc.com/getdoc.jsp?containerId=prUS44511118>

⁵ IDC. Worldwide Semiannual Augmented and Virtual Reality Spending Guide. June 2019. Available from: <https://www.idc.com/getdoc.jsp?containerId=prUS45123819>

⁶ Statista, 2019. Investment in augmented and virtual reality (AR/VR) technology worldwide in 2023, by use case. Available from: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1098345/worldwide-ar-vr-investment-use-case/>

Investment in augmented and virtual reality (AR/VR) technology worldwide in 2023, by use case (in billion U.S. dollars)

Figure 5 - Investment in AR/VR technology Worldwide in 2023, by use case.

The potential of the new technologies extends way beyond the consumer space though. According to Goldman Sachs⁷ estimates, by 2025 almost half of the industry’s revenue will be generated in the enterprise and public sector with healthcare and engineering being the most promising applications or areas of use.

In fact, Goldman Sachs’ estimate a \$35 billion AR/VR market by 2025, \$18.9 billion of which will be generated by consumer applications while \$16.1 billion will be generated by enterprise and public sector. Consumer applications will be driven by videogames, live events and video entertainment.

Figure 6 - The Diverse Potential of VR & AR Applications

⁷ Richter, F. (April 6, 2016). The Diverse Potential of VR & AR Applications [Digital image]. Retrieved May 07, 2020, from <https://www.statista.com/chart/4602/virtual-and-augmented-reality-software-revenue/>

Similar estimates from Business Insider⁸, confirm such trend. According to the company, the VR hardware and software market for **Enterprise** was estimated to be \$800 million in 2018 and is expected to reach \$5.5 billion in 2023, representing a staggering CAGR of +47.05%. Three areas will be keys to this growth: sales industry, employee training and product development.

Figure 7 - Global enterprise VR hardware and software revenue 2018-2023

2.3. Differences between former and new forecasts

Former D5.1 estimates slightly differ from the abovementioned estimates and forecasts. On the one hand, the global consumer market seems to be healthier than predicted, with a 13.5% increase over the previous forecast (\$5.9 billion instead of \$5.2 billion in 2018). We can assume this tendency will continue thanks to the release of new VR/AR headsets at lesser cost.

However, the enterprise market is not doing as well as predicted, with a 23% decrease compared to the first estimations (\$800 million instead of \$1035 million).

Region-based revenues cannot be compared since only VR was considered in the first iteration of this document, but we can see that North America and China still stands at the top of this list regarding expenditure being second and finally other Asian countries and Europe as third and fourth.

At this point, it is also worth noting that the current COVID-19 pandemic is having a major sanitary and economic impact globally. Thus, it is also important to analyse the specific impact of the pandemic on the VR/AR Market.

⁸ Business Insider. THE VR IN THE ENTERPRISE REPORT: How retailers and brands are illustrating VR's potential in sales, employee training, and product development [online]. (published December 19, 2018) Available on: <https://www.businessinsider.fr/us/virtual-reality-for-enterprise-sales-employee-training-product-2018-12>

A recent update from SuperData⁹, as of April 27th 2020, predicts the immersive technology market to have been negatively impacted by the 2020 Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemics. The 2020 forecasted figures reflect such contraction with an expected market size of \$6.3 billion, down from a prior projection.

The updated forecast by SuperData suggests a less optimistic market growth and size for the upcoming years. The estimates suggest that this market will generate \$12.2 billion in revenue by 2023, again underpinned by VR technology with a market size of \$5.3 billion, followed by AR/MR Headsets with \$4.4 billion and Mobile AR with \$2.8 billion.

The unfortunate market contraction due to COVID-19 has been mainly driven by supply chain issues which caused sales of major VR headsets to fall drastically. In parallel, location-based VR revenues, which enjoyed steady growth, have been heavily impacted due to quarantine and lockdown restrictions worldwide.

Nevertheless, it is worth noting the fact that despite COVID-19 pandemics the VR/AR market is still expected to expand at a significant rate of CAGR +24.64%. In fact, since failing sales are due to lack of supply, not demand, shipments of many headsets are expected to quickly rebound as supply chains return to normal.

In addition, as strict lockdown measures increase the demand for further immersive technology solutions, the VR/AR market is expected to drastically rebound, especially in the light of the huge adoption and upsurge of social networks, e-work and e-health platforms.

Figure 8 - Global Immersive Technology Consumer Market Revenue 2018-2023, by Segment.

⁹ SuperData, a Nielsen Company. SuperData XR Q1 2020 Update on Worldwide XR Revenue. Available from: <https://www.superdataresearch.com/blog/superdata-xr-update>

2.4. VR market adoption

Worldwide shipments of AR and VR headsets are forecasted to reach 7.6 million units in 2019, up 54.1% from the prior year according to IDC¹⁰ and as published on Statista¹¹. Strong growth is expected to continue as global shipments climb to 68.6 million in 2023 with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 66.7% over the 2019-2023 forecast period.

Forecast unit shipments of augmented (AR) and virtual reality (VR) headsets from 2019 to 2023 (in millions)

Figure 9 - Forecast shipments and AR and VR from 2019 to 2023

Interest in VR within the enterprise continues to ramp up as more companies use the technology to drive a wide range of training scenarios (see Figure 5). For instance, Statista¹² expects a positive and optimistic evolution of both Enterprise (commercial) and Consumer headsets. According to this source, commercial VR headset shipments surpassed the 1,05 million-milestones in 2018, a figure estimated to double by 2019 with 2,15 million commercial headsets shipped. By 2022, commercial VR is expected to surpass consumer VR adoption, with 16 million commercial shipments while consumer headsets shipped will account for 15,49 million.

Figure 10 - Virtual Reality Headsets Shipments by type, 2018 vs. 2019.

¹⁰ IDC, 2019. Worldwide Quarterly Augmented and Virtual Reality Headset Tracker. March 2019. Available from: <https://www.idc.com/getdoc.jsp?containerId=prUS44966319>

¹¹ Statista, 2019. Forecast unit shipments of augmented (AR) and virtual reality (VR) headsets from 2019 to 2023. Available from: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/653390/worldwide-virtual-and-augmented-reality-headset-shipments/>

¹² Statista, 2019. Virtual reality (VR) headset shipments worldwide in 2018, 2019 and 2022, by segment. June 2019. Available from: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/754860/worldwide-vr-headset-shipment-by-segment/>

Focusing on AR/VR adoption by type, while VR adoption is growing for PC-based VR, standalone VR is quickly getting more and more attention, thanks to the release of new headsets. In fact, according to SuperData¹³, Standalone adoption has substantially increased from 2018 1.6 million headset shipments to 2.8 million in 2019. On the other hand, Premium Mobile and Console adoption has slightly declined while PC VR sits flat.

Aligned with SuperData predictions, CCS Insight¹⁴ predicts that standalone VR will surpass tethered VR in number of shipments in less than two years. The mobility offered by standalone headsets should help VR to be democratized, and prices should gradually lower.

Figure 11 - Shipments of VR and AR devices worldwide

Nonetheless, we live in exceptional times, both in sanitary and economic due to the COVID-19. A recent update by IDC¹⁵, predicts a decline in VR Adoption due to a decline in AR/VR headsets shipments. However, the IDC still maintains its long terms positive forecasts with an overall optimistic outlook for the upcoming years.

For instance, 2020 shipments are predicted to suffer a 10.5% year-over-year (YoY) decline for 2020 Q1 followed by a harsher 24.1% decline in 2020 Q2. This steep decline is a result of several factors. First and foremost, the main causes are supply chain disruptions, not demand. Much of the supply chain for AR and VR headsets is shared with smartphones and PCs and many of these products are facing supply constraints as factories are operating at much lower capacity resulting in component shortages

However, the spread of the coronavirus is having the opposite effect on demand. In fact, demand is expected to ramp up during the following months as a result increasing number of consumers and employees stay indoors due to social and physical distancing measures placed by governments across the world and look to AR/VR solutions as collaborative and entertainment tools.

¹³ SuperData a Nielsen Company, 2020. 2019 Year in Review – Digital Games and Interactive Media. January 2020. Available from: <https://www.superdataresearch.com/2019-year-in-review>

¹⁴ CCS Insight. Virtual Reality Market Stumbles in 2018 [online]. (published December 3, 2018) Available on: <https://www.ccsinsight.com/blog/virtual-reality-market-stumbles-in-2018/>

¹⁵ IDC, 2020. Worldwide Quarterly Augmented and Virtual Reality Headset Tracker. 18 March 2020. Available from: <https://www.idc.com/getdoc.jsp?containerId=prUS46143720>

Assuming a scenario in which economic, production and distribution restrictions are lifted mid-year, IDC estimates a prolific second half of 2020 with nearly 7.1 million units shipped for the year, driven by increased demand, and representing a 23.6% increase from 2019. Long-term growth will be strong throughout the forecast period with shipments growing to 76.7 million units in 2024, resulting in a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 81.5%.

AR/VR Headset Shipments, Market Share, and Five-Year CAGR by Product, 2020 and 2024 (shipments in millions)						
Product Category	Product	2020 Shipments*	2020 Share*	2024 Shipments*	2024 Share*	2020—2024 CAGR*
Augmented Reality	Screenless Viewer	0.03	0.49%	0.03	0.03%	-7.07%
	Standalone HMD	0.41	5.82%	24.00	31.28%	176.39%
	Tethered HMD	0.25	3.49%	17.08	22.26%	188.45%
Virtual Reality	Screenless Viewer	0.39	5.55%	0.10	0.13%	-29.16%
	Standalone HMD	3.09	43.76%	25.25	32.92%	69.06%
	Tethered HMD	2.89	40.88%	10.26	13.38%	37.30%
TOTAL		7.06	100.00%	76.71	100.00%	81.54%

Source: IDC Worldwide Quarterly AR and VR Headset Tracker, March 18, 2020

Figure 12 - AR/VR Headset Shipments, Market Share and Five-Year CAGR by Product, 2020 and 2024.

Aligned with CCS Insights predictions, IDC predicts standalone headsets for both AR and VR to experience a steep adoption increase. Vendors are targeting both consumer and commercial buyers with the latest generation of standalone products and they are finding success in both camps. On the consumer side, gaming continues to drive growth, while on the commercial side training and collaboration are gaining additional traction. It is of especial relevance, the IDC expected commercial segment growth at a five-year CAGR of 71.9%.

Tethered Headsets are also expected to increase shipments during the forecasted period, while screenless viewers will plunge significantly as more users transition off early, value-focused products towards more robust solutions. As a result, IDC expects a CAGR of -26.5% for combined (AR & VR) screen less viewers shipments.

The following table presents an updated inventory of the SWOT matrix (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) regarding VR.

Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● HMD: wireless mobility, resolution increasing ● PC, TVM encoding and distribution technologies more mature ● Capture technologies more mature ● 360 Video capture devices more mature and affordable ● Larger IP bandwidth available ● Inside-out tracking ● 5G ● Rising of AR ● Upsurge of AR/VR demands as a result of increased online content consumption, social media, e-Work and e-Health platforms due to COVID-19. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consumers sustainably VR adoption? ● Headset acceptance? (still low resolution, heavy, expensive, not good looking) ● Potential risks of psychological deviations and sickness ● COVID-19 economic impact (economic contraction, productions shortages, supply chains disruptions, etc.).
Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● VR rebuilds the reality ● Efficiency of VR for education and training has been proven ● Helps people with disabilities & older people to develop their social interactions ● Enables cost savings for companies (fewer travels & logistics, less storage, time saving...). ● Adaptable and modular (can be moulded to adapt to specific customer requirements and market trends). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Insufficient VR content today ● Lack of synchronization and realism ● Poor self-representation / avatar ● Lack of interoperability in the ecosystem

Table 1 - VR SWOT Analysis

An unprecedented market disruptor, for instance the COVID-19 pandemic, is completely shaking the global market and economy and, by extension the VR/AR Market where VR Together operates in. It is for this reason that major market changes have occurred during the course of the last months, completely changing the global panorama, arising multiple new threats as well as opportunities. It is for this reason that the VR SWOT analysis incorporated multiple new inputs.

First and foremost, the COVID-19 pandemic has generated an unprecedented economic impact, disrupting global supply chains and negatively impacting on businesses and even end-users. This represents a major threat for the VR market, which needs to be closely monitored.

On the other hand, due to the pandemic and the quarantine restrictions imposed by governments to control the virus, has led to an upsurge of online content consumption and e-Work and e-Health adoption. As a result, the demand for VR/AR technologies have greatly increased since these technologies have the potential to serve businesses and end-users in multiple applications ranging from entertainment, social platforms, conferences, meetings, etc.

Another important change has been the fact that inside-out tracking that is more and more used. **Inside-out tracking** permits an easier setup of VR headsets, since users only need to plug in their headsets to make the whole system work – where they previously needed to carefully place the sensor’s bases before being able to do anything. Inside-out tracking should help VR to spread more widely, since it’s easier to use.

2.5. VR usage

Since we analysed and discussed VR usage from the customers’ point of view in V1, we will now focus on VR usage from industrial perspective. For this matter, VR industry reports from Perkins Coie¹⁶, released on an annual basis, represents an industry reference and provides valuable and insightful data.

The last published report from March 2019, with 200 respondents from various industries highlights which are the most applicable industries for XR technology adoption and uptake. For instance, 61% of the respondents stated that the Gaming Industry is where XR technologies may be most applicable, followed by Healthcare and Medical devices; and Education industries both concentrating a 41%.

> In which industries do you believe XR is most applicable at this time?
(Please select up to 3 options)

¹⁶ Perkins Coie LLP, 2019. Augmented And Virtual Reality Survey Report 2019. March 2019. Available from: <https://www.perkinscoie.com/images/content/2/1/v4/218679/2019-VR-AR-Survey-Digital-v1.pdf>

Figure 13 - Industries where XR is the most applicable currently

Interestingly such figures match the sectors where the most investment is directed to the development of AR/VR technology in the next 12 months, according to survey respondents. Nonetheless, when analysing previous three-years industrial survey responses to which market segments and applications investments are going to be directed to; an interesting shift in the trend can be appreciated.

While gaming applications concentrated most of investment directions in 2016 with a 78% investment focus, the trend has slowly declined although it is still expected to witness the most investment directed to development for the next 12 months (54%). Nevertheless, responders provided a fairly diversified look at promise in other industries, especially with regard to healthcare and medical devices and education. Compared to previous surveys, both healthcare and medical devices (26% in 2018) and education (26% in 2018) have seen huge increases in the expectation for investment in the next 12 months. Workforce development came in for the first time at rather impressive 15%.

Combined with D5.1 data, we can see that both consumers and industrials agree that gaming and education are domains where VR is the most applicable. Industrials also think that the healthcare sector has good prospects for VR.

VR/AR/MR/XR technology and content investment focus worldwide from 2016 to 2019

Figure 14 - VR/AR/MR/XR technology investment directions worldwide 2016-2019.

In the light of this figures it is clear that technology-wise the market is ready, but it remains unclear how long it will take before broad adoption. Several market obstacles and restraints need to be successfully overcome in order to enable mass adoption of such technologies.

For instance, Perkins Coie identifies User experience deficiencies as the most important market obstacle for mass adoption (27%). The lack of VR content and consumer and business reluctant to embrace AR/VR follows close behind with a 20% and 19% rate. Importantly, 10% of respondents mention regulatory and legal risks as an important market barrier.

> What is the biggest obstacle to mass adoption of AR and VR technologies?
Select one for each technology:

Figure 15 - Reasons for non-adoption of the VR technology

Retrospectively, a dichotomy regarding market barriers becomes evident as, while cost restraints were the 1st reason for non-adoption according to customers, in this industry survey it falls down to almost last position (11%). Nevertheless, both industrials and consumers, equally envision the lack of content as an important restraint in VR adoption (2nd place in both surveys).

Be that as it may, VR usage is on the rise, demand is rising, and investments are growing across several sectors, which combined provide an optimistic outlook for market with plenty of opportunities for the upcoming years.

In addition, The Venture Reality Fund has found in their 2019 report that growth areas appear to be gaming, location-based entertainment, enterprise and healthcare. Enterprise VR has developed in a number of ways, with dedicated hardware and software: new headsets, new applications for training and entertainment, etc.

The Venture Reality Fund also released their annual poster¹⁷; which cites the most influential companies in VR. This time, only companies making revenue with VR have been kept.

¹⁷ The Venture Reality Fund. Industry Landscape [online]. (published May, 2019) Available on: <http://www.thevrfund.com/resources/industry-landscape/>

THE VR FUND 2019 VR INDUSTRY LANDSCAPE

Figure 16 - The VR Fund industry landscape

2.6. Augmented Reality: a new opportunity on the rise

Since the first iteration of this document, some VR actors have changed their strategy, or completely abandoned VR.

For example, in November 2019, IMAX closed their only VR room in Europe and announced their plans to close their 3 remaining rooms in North America. This closure puts an end to their 2-year VR experimentation. In 2016, IMAX invested around \$50 million on VR content, and built 7 rooms all around the world. These rooms provided a “premium VR experience” with exclusive movies and haptic feedback. But the short content (less than 20 minutes) and the high price tag deterred patrons. Acknowledging this failure, IMAX first decided to transform those rooms into VR arcades, and finally shut them down completely.

Google also decided to shut down some of their activities related to Daydream, their VR platform. The new smartphone of the firm is not compatible with the platform, and the Google Play Movies & TV portal has been removed from Daydream. While no official announcement has been made about the future of Daydream, it’s clear that Google is slowing down their investments in this sector.

But there are still actors actively investing in VR. Facebook, for example, is working on a system of super realistic avatars to implement it into Oculus. To the difference of VRTogether which focuses on a real-time rendering of users, Facebook chose to create 3D avatars based on pictures of the user and animate them afterwards by replicating the user’s movements.

Figure 17- Facebook’s avatars

In a similar fashion, VRTogether is focused on virtual reality. Nonetheless during the past few years, the market for augmented reality is witnessing a huge growth and is becoming more and more popular. This market shift attracted some VR players attention and interest in this technology, a market shift that VR Together is well aware off.

For instance, a clear sign of this shifting trend is the difference between VR and AR installed base. As previously mentioned, VR requires the use of specialised equipment’s such as headsets and cameras. Despite AR also may require specialised equipment, one of the biggest applications is virtual objects by using computer vision. The so-called Mobile AR has been massively adopted thanks to AR capable smartphones.

It is no surprise then that AR installed base outperforms by several-fold figures VR installed based, since AR capable smartphones are almost on everyone’s pockets nowadays. According

to Digi-Capital¹⁸, Mobile AR installed base has witnessed a staggering increase and is expected to reach the 500 million AR capable devices by 2021. Mobile VR and Console/PC VR is lagging behind, mainly due to barriers such as cost, user experience and lack of content as mentioned in section 2.5. Be that as it may, as outlined in section 2.4 VR shipments are steadily increasing and are also expected to witness a substantial increase in installed base.

Figure 18 - VR/AR Installed base (in million)

¹⁸ Digi-Capital, 2017. After mixed year, mobile AR to drive \$108 billion VR/AR market by 2021. January 13, 2017. Available from: <https://www.digi-capital.com/news/2017/01/after-mixed-year-mobile-ar-to-drive-108-billion-vrar-market-by-2021/>

2.6.1. Defining AR

Augmented Reality is the addition of virtual objects in a real environment, contrary to Virtual Reality where the environment is also simulated. To render those virtual objects, it mostly relies on computer vision.

AR can be used for many applications, from gaming to publications and industrial training. Today, AR is widely implemented in smartphones (thanks to libraries like Google's AR-Core¹⁹ or Apple's ARKit²⁰), and specific devices for AR usage are being developed (for example the Magic Leap One, or the Hololens).

Figure 19-AR is commonly implemented in smartphones and used in many apps.

2.6.2. Actors switching from VR to AR

Even though VR should have more revenue than AR in the following years (i.e. 2.1), a number of VR players decided to leave the VR field and to focus on the AR sector. Mimesys²¹ for example, who once was a direct competitor of VRTogether, changed their focus from VR to AR. The enterprise is now using Magic Leap One headsets for their technology, and has subsequently been bought by the Magic Leap group, who praised their communication and collaboration solution.

This change can be explained by the lesser amount of power needed to render AR compared to VR, making it more easily exploitable. We can also postulate that since smartphones can be used as AR devices, the market is already available, while not many persons possess either a VR headset or a smartphone powerful enough to run VR simulations.

With these modifications from their competitors, VRTogether's teams considered a possible AR version of the platform. While VRTogether isn't built to be used in AR, it could be possible to adapt it fairly easily, thanks to how every component is designed.

¹⁹ <https://developers.google.com/ar>

²⁰ <https://developer.apple.com/augmented-reality/>

²¹ <https://www.mimesysvr.com/>

3. HARDWARE & COMPONENTS

In this section, we will overview the brand-new hardware related to the VRTogether project that has been announced or released since V1. Keeping track of hardware novelties is essential to keep a clear sight of VRTogether’s future.

In market terms, Hardware is predicted to concentrate half of VR revenues by 2020, although Consumer and Enterprise software/services is predicted to quickly grow and concentrate an ever-increasing share. For instance, this trend follows the fact that first hardware needs to be broadly adopted and deployed before specific software/services can be launched.

This important VR market pattern/evolution is of great relevance since depicts the software/services dependence on hardware adoption and progress in the field of VR. For instance, SuperData 2017 forecast predicted hardware to dominate the VR market, a situation that has prolonged until 2019. Nowadays, hardware is beginning to become sufficiently available for specific software/services to flourish given that there is a minimum viable installed base to bring sustainable revenues.

SuperData predicts that hardware will represent, in 2020, \$17.8 billion out of the \$37.7 billion VR Market, or roughly a 47,21% share. However, it is expected that software/services will grow at a faster pace than hardware slowly concentrating an increasing share of the market. It should be noted that this 2017 SuperData predictions may be outdated or biased from more up-to-date forecast in terms of market size and revenues but provides a clear outlook of how VR hardware and software are interconnected marketwise.

Figure 20 - Worldwide VR revenue by segment from 2016 to 2020

As mentioned, and despite the improvements, hardware adoption is still lagging behind although it is expected to improve drastically in the upcoming times as better, faster, more mature technologies launch to the market and product prices drop. It is therefore crucial for VR Together to acknowledge the importance of the VR Hardware market so as to enable future positive commercial outcomes.

In this context, Consumer-focused VR companies continue their search for the semi-mythical killer app that would make VR a real success. The market remains dominated by gaming applications, but we can see traction in areas such as live streaming and social media. Over the next few years, players in this sector will face a battle for supremacy against related technologies, especially augmented reality (AR).

On one hand, Sony currently dominates the VR hardware and headset market, ahead of Oculus (Facebook) and HTC. It remains dedicated to gaming, while Oculus and HTC are racing to capture both consumer and enterprise markets. On the other side, Samsung is falling behind in VR. Its low-cost Gear VR is struggling on both the hardware and content fronts, while the premium Samsung HMD Odyssey's popularity has been limited by its high price. The latest announcement from Qualcomm of its new Snapdragon XR2 5G Reference Design²² may influence the market and improve the quality of end user experience.

3.1. Headsets

Nowadays, one of the primary concerns of VR users is the lack of mobility induced by the wired connections of HMDs to a PC. Therefore, companies are investing into wireless extensions for existing devices and standalone headsets.

In 2018, Oculus released a standalone HMD called Oculus Go. Even if the headset was praised for its comfort and ease of use, the 3 DoF sensors and the lack of applications were two serious drawbacks. With the new Oculus Quest, launched in May 2019, the enterprise aims to correct those mistakes and to offer a better VR experience with a 6 DoF sensor that allows the user to move freely in his surroundings, and a large catalogue of applications thanks to an access to the same store than the Rift. This headset also embeds a Qualcomm Snapdragon 835 processor, more powerful than the Go's one, and two controllers identical to the Rift's ones. This headset was priced at 449€ for a version with 64 GB of storage (549€ for 128 GB), and was shipping on the 21st May 2019.

In response to the release of Oculus Go, Oculus' competitor HTC released in 2018 the Vive Focus. With the same processor and a slightly better resolution, HTC decided to aim this new headset at businesses.

A few months later, its evolution was announced. Soberly called Focus Plus, it was released on the 15th April 2019. While its specifications are the same as the Focus' ones, the former 3 DoF controller is replaced by two 6 DoF controllers. It also contains Fresnel lenses of better quality and was sold at 995€.

Figure 21 - HTC Vive Focus Plus

²² <https://www.qualcomm.com/products/snapdragon-xr2-5g-platform>

But even though standalone devices are on the rise, there's still a huge market for tethered HMDs. While Oculus and HTC try to maintain their hegemony on this segment by releasing updated versions of their headsets, incoming challengers aim to offer new alternatives.

The successor of the Oculus Rift, the Rift S, is packing an LCD panel instead of an OLED panel but offers a higher resolution. The Room Scale system with external sensors has been replaced by an internal set of cameras. The Rift S was released on the 21st May 2019, and cost 449€, the same date and price as its standalone counterpart.

Vive also worked on a new version of its Vive Pro, called Vive Pro Eye. It pretty much consists of a Vive Pro with an added eye tracking feature. The Vive Pro Eye is available to buy in the UK, for a price of 1649€. The company is also working on a new headset called Vive Cosmos, planned to release on Q3 2019. This headset would be compatible with PC and smartphones and features a larger resolution than the original Vive.

As for newcomers, Valve, former partner of HTC and specialized in the gaming industry, announced their first VR headset, the Valve Index, on the 1st of May 2019. Shipping on the 28th of June 2019, the full bundle cost 1079€, and contains a headset, two base stations for room-scale tracking, and two controllers. Its strong points are a 120Hz screen refreshing rate, that can be upscale to an experimental 144Hz mode, and a finger-tracking system included in the controllers. It also features a front hole with a USB 3.0 port to place future accessories in it.

3.1.1. New generation of headsets

First-gen headsets used external sensors to track the position of the user or didn't use anything at all. Computer-assisted vision (cameras used on the headset) can simplify tracking of users and controllers (including hands)

- Easier system configuration
- Greater freedom of movement

Although tracking the user's position in the environment has progressed significantly to the point where it's available in mass market offerings, controller and eye tracking are not yet widely adopted and need to develop further. Minor progress made in displays from the previous generation

- Larger resolution
- Very little change in field of view or refresh rates.

Prices are still high despite more mature solutions. A two-fold difference in price exists between "consumer" and professional headsets (approx. 400 USD vs 800 USD). Still two different modes of operation, tethered and standalone, but with more flexible headsets offering both modes emerging (e.g. HTC Vive Cosmos, Oculus Quest with optional Oculus Link).

Product	Oculus Quest	Oculus rift S	HTC Vive focus Plus	HTC Vive cosmos	Valve Index	Qualcomm XR2
Launch date	May 2019	May 2019	April 2019	Nov 2019	May 2019	Feb 2020
Price	449 € 64Go 549 128 Go	449 €	995€	799€	540€ 1079€ (Full Pack)	Ref Design for manufacturer
Target market	Consumers	Consumers	Enterprise	Consumers	Consumers	Both
Type	Standalone	PC tethered	Standalone	PC tethered	PC tethered	5G-enabled HMD
Resolution	1440 x 1600 per eye	1280 x 1440 per eye	1440 x 1600 per eye	1440 x 1700 per eye	1440x1600 per eye	Up to 3000 x 3000 per eye
Screen	OLED	LCD	AMOLED	LCD	LCD	N/A

Table 2 - New generation of headsets

3.1.2. Internal Hardware Vendor: Qualcomm

As the virtual reality technology has advanced, its access is now being widely available, ranging from business and professional applications to customer-level or particular use. Regardless of the end-use, VR technologies require important, dedicated and specialized hardware component, among of all, the most important and critical is Central Processing Unit – CPU.

An important difference exists between tethered or standalone VR devices and even smartphone AR, and that is where the CPU is located. In the case of tethered VR solutions, the VR processing is run on a PC. On the other hand, standalone VR devices need to run all the digital processing within the headset. Needless to say, important differences exist in terms of space, heat reduction, etc. between the two and, as a result, specifically designed and optimised CPU can be found on the market for each use

For tethered solutions which require a PC to run the VR experience, we have identified two important stakeholders: Intel and Advanced Micro Devices (AMD).

On the one hand, the tech giant AMD has recently released a set of VR ready processors and VR graphics card to power the demanding VR workloads. This is the case of AMD Ryzen 7 1800x CPU, high-quality processor designed for high-performance video encoding, content streaming and gaming at 4k resolution. It is a fast desktop processor with 8 cores and 16 threads that provides ultimate performance and value for gamers and creators. Simultaneous Multi-threading allows each core to handle two simultaneous threads as if they are two virtual processors. However, it has important limitations such as the need for a Ryzen-7 compatible cooler and the fact that overclocking may result in disabling extended frequency range and precision boost which may negatively impact of processing, and ultimately on the user experience.

In conclusion, The Ryzen-7 1800X processor is the fastest of the first generation Ryzen processors. A number of architectural advances have been combined with all new processing technologies to propel users to the next horizon of computing. It provides great multi-core performance along with smooth gaming with strong minimum frame rate. It is considered as one of the best processors fastest and latest processors because of its capability to run VR and allowing its users to experience the Virtual world.

On the other hand, the world-renowned Intel also offers multiple CPU that are VR ready. The top-notch Intel Core i9-9980XE leads the way being the fastest high-end desktop processor available on the market. This CPU is based on Intel's Skylake architecture which is fabricated on 14nm process and with its 18 cores and 36 threads allow the processor to run multiple programs simultaneously. Perhaps, the most interesting feature is that thank to its massive capabilities it allows 4k VR videos. Nonetheless, the processor does not contain any integrated graphics and its price tag makes of this processor only attractive for professional or business purposes.

Regarding standalone VR Devices CPU, Qualcomm stands-out as one of the most important stakeholders, if not, currently the most important one. Qualcomm is a big stakeholder in the HMD market; they are not only headsets manufacturers but also provide the main chipset to run them. With most of the high-end mobile phones (except iPhone) already using Qualcomm a chip, the company is now expanding to the HMD market. Already more than 30 AR and VR headsets use Qualcomm chips, with Oculus Quest the most popular one.

The newest chip, Snapdragon XR2²³, features a lot: 5G-enabled extended reality system, which should allow for experiences that rely on low latency, super-fast data connections. The Snapdragon XR2 offers double the CPU and GPU performance of its predecessors allowing for 8K, 360-degree video playback and supporting display panels as pixel-dense as 3K by 3K per eye running at 90 frames per second.

Figure 22- Qualcomm Snapdragon - XR2 5G

That extra horsepower and those higher-res screens should all go a long way in helping the next generation of extended reality experiences feel more immersive. A new, dedicated AI engine in the XR2 can handle processes like object and voice recognition, 3D reconstruction, depth detection and more up to 11 times faster than the earlier XR1 chipset.

The XR2 also supports up to seven on-device cameras at once -- with the help of a custom vision processor, XR2-powered devices will be able to track the user's head, eyes, hands and even lips. That's especially important when you consider that one of Qualcomm's big goals going forward is popularizing mixed reality -- in this case, that means using some of those cameras to pass video data straight through to the eye displays, and laying virtual objects on top of those real-world scenes.

²³ <https://www.qualcomm.com/products/snapdragon-xr2-5g-platform>

3.2. Capture systems

3.2.1. Hardware

The volumetric video market is expected to grow from \$578.3 million in 2018 to \$2.78 billion by 2023²⁴. A recent 2020 report by Research and Markets²⁵ not only confirms this trend but also expects to grow at a faster pace, from the \$1.4 billion market size of 2020 to the \$5.8 billion by 2025, at CAGR of +32.8% for the forecasted period.

The market is fuelled by the rising demand of the technology in events, creative advertisement, exhibitions, presentations and conferences. For instance, several world leading companies invest in this sector.

For example, Facebook at the end of September 2018 unveiled a volumetric 360-degree camera built in collaboration with RED Digital Cinema²⁶. Known as the Manifold, the new system may be first and foremost a VR camera, but volumetric cameras also hold great promise to the traditional video industry. Volumetric cameras such as the Manifold can create more immersive and compelling virtual reality content. Volumetric video will present new workflow challenges. Facebook has partnered with post-production software companies, including Adobe, CaraVR, Nuke, Foundry, Otoy and others, to build out the workflow for video of this kind.

Figure 23 - Manifold 3D VR camera

In January 2018, Intel opened a volumetric video studio in Los Angeles. Its approach to volumetric video comes from the outside. Rather than a single system capturing the scene from the inside out, like Manifold, Intel Studios surrounds the 10,000-square-foot capture area with dozens and dozens of cameras.²⁷

²⁴ Volumetric Video Market by Volumetric Capture, Application , & Content Delivery and Region - Global Forecast to 2025, MARKETS AND MARKETS: <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/volumetric-video-market-259585041.html>

²⁵ Research and Markets, 2020. Volumetric Video Market – Global Forecasts to 2025. February 2020.

²⁶ <https://facebook360.fb.com/2018/09/26/film-the-future-with-red-and-facebook-360/>

²⁷ <https://variety.com/2019/digital/features/intel-studios-volumetric-capture-holograms-ar-vr-1203358126/>

Figure 24 - Inside Intel Studios, the World's Largest Volumetric Capture Stage

Intel RealSense²⁸ technology is changing the future of 3D imaging by providing high speed stereoscopic vision in an embedded package with a large depth of field. The robustness of the system makes it very versatile to cover an extensive variety of usage models - both for indoors or outdoors applications - by providing sophisticated setup and calibration tools. The core of the system, the unique Intel RealSense Vision Processor D4, uses advanced algorithms to process raw image streams from the depth cameras and computes high resolution 3D depth maps without the need for dedicated GPU or host processor. A variety of depth modules and housed camera devices provide an easy solution for rapid integration into industrial vision systems.

The Azure Kinect sensor has a 12 megapixel RGB camera supplemented by 1 megapixel-depth camera for body tracking. It also has a 360-degree seven-microphone array and an orientation sensor. The Azure Kinect is used in volumetric capture workflows through the use of software tools such as Depthkit or EF EVE which allows the highest number of Azure Kinects to be connected into one consumer friendly volumetric capture rig. These software allow users to create interactive virtual reality experiences with human performances

Google also has a hand in the volumetric video game. When light field camera maker Lytro shut its doors, Google hired plenty of the company's employees. Light field cameras record light from every direction through every point and space and use this information to map out a space in 3D. For example, Lytro's Immerge camera system offered about one meter of free movement for viewers, as well as more realistic texture and lighting. Although Lytro's camera technology could also allow creators to change depth of field, focal point, shutter speed and aperture in post, and eliminate the need to use a green screen for visual effects, the company changed its strategy and focused more on VR in 2015.

²⁸https://www.intelrealsense.com/stereo_depth/?utm_source=intelcom_website&utm_medium=button&utm_campaign=day-to-day&utm_content=D400_learn-more_button

Product	MICROSOFT AZURE KINECT ²⁹	Microsoft® Kinect™ 2.0 ³⁰	ASUS® XtionPro™ Live ³⁰	Intel® RealSense™ Camera D435 ³¹	Stereolabs® ZED™ ³²	Orbbec® Astra Mini™ ³³	MYNT EYE ³⁴
Frame Rate	30fps	30 fps	30 fps	30-90 fps	15 fps at max res., 120 fps at VGA res	30 fps	60 fps
Depth Range	0.25 to 5.46 m	0.5 to 4.5 m	0.8 to 3.5 m	0.105 to 10 m	0.3 - 25 m	0.6 m to 5.0 m	0.5 to 18 m
Type	Time-of- flight	Time of flight	Structured light	Active IR Stereo using Global Shutter Sensors and IMU	Embedded stereo	Structured Light	Stereo Camera
3D Resolution	320x288 to 1024x1024	512 x 424	640 x 480	1280 x 720 max	2208 x 1242 max	640 x 480 max	752x480

Table 3 - Capture system

3.2.2. 3D Sensors³⁵

Three dimensional sensors are depth sensing devices which aims at connecting the dives with the real world by using projected light and a camera system. According to Industry ARC³⁶, the global 3D sensor market was valued \$1.9 billion in 2017 and is expected to grow at an impressive CAGR of +26.54% for the 2018-2023 period, to reach a market size of \$8.1 billion by 2023.

3D sensors have a broad-spectrum application with multiple end user industries and consumer segments including, healthcare, consumer electronics, robotics, etc. Interestingly, the 3D sensors market is expected to specifically expand into gaming and face-recognition applications. Major players of the market, like Sony Corp, Samsung Electronics, Raytric, Omnivision, are investing and developing 3D sensing technologies to cater these specific market segments.

²⁹ <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/services/kinect-dk/>

³⁰ https://www.asus.com/gr/3D-Sensor/Xtion_PRO_LIVE/

³¹ <https://www.intelrealsense.com/depth-camera-d435i/>

³² <https://www.stereolabs.com/zed/>

³³ <https://orbbec3d.com/astra-mini-series/>

³⁴ <https://www.mynteye.com/>

³⁵ <https://rosindustrial.org/3d-camera-survey>

³⁶ Industry ARC (Furion Analytics Research & Consulting LLP., 2019. 3D Sensors Market – Forecast (2020 – 2025). Available from: <https://www.industryarc.com/Report/244/global-3d-sensor-market-analysis-report.html>

For instance, the company Raytrix³⁷ is a German developer of plenoptic cameras since 2009. They have, up until now, primarily focused on using this technology for industrial imaging solutions. They offer a range of complete plenoptic cameras which can create a depth map and 3D reconstruction accurately. Their new technology includes cameras with lightfield image-sensors. Using the entry level R5 camera one has full control in digital post processing of the perspective and focus setting of the captured pictures. Also, a 3D reconstruction of the original scene is possible. The difference of the new Raytrix cameras compared to standard cameras consists of the modified image-sensor (CMOS) and a special software package, by which one can interpret and modify pictures in real-time afterwards.

The company Matterport³⁸ works with a wide range of digital cameras which give the flexibility to create spaces of any size, scale, and complexity. Matterport's 3D capture platform is compatible with sophisticated Lidar cameras including the Leica BLK360 for increased precision and range along with a family of affordable 360 cameras for ease and convenience of capturing a digital twin. The Pro2 Camera is 12-23 megapixels and can transform 2D images into an immersive and accurate 3D experience.

3.3. Identified components from the project

Within all the different hardware and other components that are needed for VR, there are a few of them which are of critical importance for VRTogether's project. For instance, the components described below is where several VRTogether's developments are encompassed within and thus, examining their current status, availability and trends in the market is vital.

It is therefore necessary to provide an in-depth market overview of the current state of the art and market landscape for these components.

3.3.1. Point-Cloud Capture and encoding systems

Point clouds allow a simple point wise representation of geometry without complex pre-processing as compared to other prevalent 3D representations, such as watertight meshes. This however results in higher requirements regarding storage space, making them too large to stream directly over bandwidth limited networks. As a result, compression of point clouds has received significant commercial and research interest in recent years.

Octree based point cloud codecs allow for an efficient representation of geometry in addition to low delay coding using octree occupancy. Some of the open source solutions available include the Point Cloud Library with the codec proposed by Kammerl et al. [10]. Mekuria et al [7] also present an open source point cloud codec that allows for inter frame coding as well as attribute coding using projection and JPEG compression. Signal processing-based point cloud codecs such as the codec proposed by Queroz et al. [9] allow for more efficient attribute coding but incur higher encode and decode time for pre-processing including a repeated eigen decomposition.

Open source mesh codecs such as Draco [2] and Corto [1] also support point cloud compression by treating the point locations as vertices of a mesh. They directly quantize the vertex locations making them unsuitable for lossy compression to low bitrates for streaming. These codecs are better suited to be used in near lossless compression configurations.

The ISO standards body MPEG launched a point cloud compression standardization activity [11] in 2017 with a call for proposals. They are currently developing two classes of solutions.

³⁷ <https://raytrix.de/>

³⁸ <https://matterport.com/cameras>

Video based compression (V-PCC) that projects point cloud geometry and attributes to 2D and then leverages 2D video coding technologies.

This class of solutions have high encoder complexity but allow for low delay decoding especially if hardware acceleration on modern GPUs are used to decode the video streams. The second class of solutions are 3D geometry based (G-PCC) that represent geometry using a hierarchical structure of voxels. These solutions have the advantage of being native 3D representations and offer a potential for future optimizations based on human perception of 3D point clouds. These solutions also allow for configurations that offer low delay encoding and decoding. The final standard is expected to be published in 2020 and contributed by major companies in the field.

With the increased commercial and research interest in point cloud compression several datasets have been made available to evaluate and benchmark codec performance. Alexiadis et al [4] provided an early sparse point cloud dataset that was used to develop the anchor codec for the MPEG standardization activity. After the launch of the MPEG call for proposals dense photorealistic point cloud datasets became available including the 8i voxelized full bodies [6] and Microsoft voxelised upper bodies [5] datasets. Recently a few more mesh-based datasets have been made available that can be used to create or sample point clouds. This includes the 3D people dataset [8] and the Microsoft Rocketbox avatar library [3]. By applying animations to the avatars and sampling points from the mesh surface a point cloud dataset can be created from this library.

The point cloud compression solution used in the project, unlike the other approaches, allows for real-time delivery as needed for communication and encodes the geometry natively, so it enables optimisation based on human perception. Moreover, the project intends to contribute a new dataset that will allow for better evaluation of compression solutions. The dataset will be captured in realistic conditions and representative of socialVR activities.

This aspect, we believe, is of critical importance to solve one of the main barriers for mass adoption of VR technologies: the lack of quality in content (See Figure 15). In this regard, a distinction needs to be made. Quality, as perceived by users, refers to multiple factors, such as immersion, interactivity, communications, among many others. All of them, however, require real-time delivery of information packages to ensure smoothness of the experience. Another, critical aspect is to deliver a human-like perception experience of the environment, in terms of volumetric and geometric representation, independently of the realism or non-realism of the virtual representation. Hence, since point cloud compression directly impacts on quality performance of VR we believe that its inclusion in the project will enable a better adoption by end-users.

3.3.2. Real time 4D Capture systems

Most volumetric capturing systems require complex set up processes with cumbersome hardware setup, while some of them require special capturing environment (green screen) (Table 5) and need heavy human operations from specially trained staff. This raises an obstacle towards their commercialization and makes them to target only a small part of the market, the one which is eager to pay high amounts of money to acquire 3D content (Table 4). Heavy customization in materials and configurations is also limiting their portability. In addition, most capturing, and calibration software systems are private while it remains hard to assemble and/or develop them.

Company	Pricing
---------	---------

VRTogether volumetric capturing	Public SW, Affordable HW
EF EVE	From \$39
Depthkit	From \$10.00
Breke	From \$40
Metastage	From \$15K
4D views	Over \$100k
dimension	
INVR.space GmbH	
Mantis Vision	
Volucap	
3dMD	Project Based
4DR Studios	
8i Premium stage	
dimension studio mobile	
DoubleMe	
Evercoast	
HoloCap	
Holosee	
HypeVR	
Mark Roberts Motion Control	
Volograms	

Table 4 -Volumetric capturing solutions pricing

The majority of competition (with few exceptions) offers high-budget solutions (Table 4). **VRTogether approach is to publicly offer a multi-view system based on recent sensor technology that is significantly lower cost, easier to set up and portable which is achieved through careful design decisions.** The VRTogether 4D capture system can be used for 3D content creation by freelancers and professionals enabling quicker workflows due to quicker and more flexible setup times. Table 5 showcases commercial volumetric capturing systems. As we can observe, most of them use numerous cameras/sensors to acquire their content. However, there are systems such as the ones from 4Dviews, Depthkit, EF EVE, Evercoast and HoloCap that are the real competitors of VRTogether as they claim to use equivalent number of cameras/sensors as VRTogether's system.

4DViews³⁹ offers a Volumetric Video Capture System called HOLOSYS. This volumetric video capture system has been designed to equip professional creative studios, with high quality, flexible and intuitive solutions compatible with the most popular VR, AR, MR & VFX technologies. HOLOSYS includes 4DViews hardware for performance captation, and 4DViews' volumetric system software to generate high quality volumetric video sequences. HOLOSYS offers adjustable equipment. Multiple HOLOSYS configurations can be set. Processing speed can be increased as an option with a capture rate up to 60 fps.

³⁹ <https://www.4dviews.com/holosys-volumetric-video-system>

Depthkit⁴⁰ is the world's most widely used solution for volumetric video capture for AR, VR and MR. Depthkit captures the world in depth and color creating immersive experiences for XR, and distinctive content for film and video by adding 3D capture to any content production workflow. Depthkit provides a pipeline from capture to publishing, using familiar video production workflows. On set, Depthkit captures color and depth data from a depth sensor and can be paired with any professional camera.

EF EVE™⁴¹ is one of the most popular volumetric capture software for editing and distribution tools for volumetric video. It offers the ability to use multiple Azure Kinect cameras and record, edit, export and publish volumetric videos. EF EVE™ supports the most popular 3D cameras such as Azure Kinect, Realsense 415 and 435, Kinect V2 (XBOX ONE). EF EVE™.

Company	Cameras/Sensors	Green screen required	Capture rate
VRTogether 4D capture.	2-8 RGBD sensors	No	15 and 30 fps (depending on the preference)
3dMD	10 to 30-plus modular units of 30 to 90-plus machine vision cameras	No	10-120 fps
4D views	8 volumetric capture pods	Yes (or chroma key)	up to 60 fps
4DR Studios	32 calibrated RGB cameras	Yes	30-60fps
8i Portable stage	30 Camera Resolution: HD 1920 x 1080	Yes	15-30fps
8i Premium stage	30 Cameras Resolution:UHD 4096 x 3000	Yes	15- 30 fps
Brekel	Portable setup: 1 or 2 Kinect V2, V1, Orbbec Astra, Astra Pro, Intel RealSense	No	30fps
Depthkit	Single sensor.(Azure Kinect or Kinect v2 or RealSense D400 Depth Cameras)	No	30fps
Dimension studio	106 -110 cameras (53 RGB cameras which read colour, 53 IR cameras that record depth)	No	30-60 fps
Dimension studio mobile	106-110 cameras (55 RGB cameras which read colour, 55 IR cameras that record depth)	No	30-60 fps
DoubleMe	1 camera. HoloPortal™ converts 2D video into dynamic 3D models in real-time	No	NA
EF EVE	1 to 8 Azure Kinect, Kinect v2 or Intel RealSense sensors	No	5-15-30 fps
Evercoast	Scalable, 2-20+ cameras, standard rig-two dozen cameras on metal poles.	Yes	NA
HoloCap	1 low cost depth camera (Kinect V2)-Multicamera support in progress	No	30-90fps
HypeVR	14 high-end Red cameras and a Velodyne LiDAR scanner	Yes	up to 90 fps
Mantis Vision	3D Handheld Scanners	No	8 fps
Metastage	106 cameras and 8 shotgun microphones (53 IR + 53 RGB, 12MP sensors), IR texture projectors, 16 Channel Sennheiser Audio Recording System	Yes	30-60 fps

⁴⁰ <https://www.depthkit.tv/>

⁴¹ <https://ef-eve.com/volumetric-capture/>

Volucap	32 Custom cameras, 20MP global shutter cameras with 12 Bit of raw recording	No	NA
Volumetric Camera Systems	Expandable dome grid array (70x Sony 4K Cameras)	No	30-60fps
Zubr	custom rigs consisting of Kinect V2s, Intel Realsense and Stereolabs ZED cameras	Yes	NA

Table 5 - Commercial volumetric capturing solutions

Users behind the capturing scene expect a capturing system that will be as easy as possible to install and use so that they spend more time on the creative part of a captured performance and worry less about technical details. To address this VRTogether offers a solution that requires minimum or not at all training which provides a comparative advantage from others that need special trained operators. This an important aspect for the positive adoption of the VR solution, since smoothness in user experience is a key aspect for positive VR adoption, as depicted in figure 15. The fact that basic users are able to perform system set up and capturing will boost its adoption from a wide target group. Creative studios need affordable hardware and software and prefer solutions with ease of portability. Furthermore, they need systems that require minimum storage space while keeping a good content quality balance. Post processing of data from many depth sensors needs significant computing sources. An important advantage of VRTogether is that it can support an arbitrary number of sensors (2-8 RGBD sensors). Using a small number of sensors contributes towards keeping storage space needs low and thus decreasing post processing load and corresponding costs.

Another characteristic that users require is realistic volumetric capturing in high quality while keeping capturing in real time. Furthermore, they need a quick, robust, user friendly and affordable depth sensor calibration process which is the starting point of every capturing system. VRTogethers' capturing system enables the generation of high-quality realistic 3D assets (color HD to FHD, depth 320x180 - 640x576) meeting creators' needs.

At the same time, it requires minimum equipment; it is portable and easy to use. VRTogethers' capturing and calibration software is free and publicly available.⁴²

⁴² <https://github.com/VCL3D/VolumetricCapture>

Figure 25 - VRTogether 4D capture system Value Proposition Canvas

3.3.3. Volumetric data end to end transmission

Point clouds used to be statically captured, recorded as files, and reloaded. Thus, typical usage was offline for 3D designs used in video games, medical applications, mapping applications (military, google maps, ...). These applications have appeared in the mid-90s with VRML (Virtual Reality Modeling Language) and then X3D that were superseded by waves of newer technologies. With the standardization efforts at MPEG on MPEG codecs (V-PCC and G-PCC res. due in 2020 and 2021), MPEG is also going to offer transmission support for popular streaming protocols such as MPEG-DASH.

Existing platforms with a commercial background are mostly based on Google Draco compression. It is interesting to notice that Draco supports both point clouds and meshes, exactly as VR Together does. Draco fits well with Khronos standardization efforts, in particular glTF (GL Transmission Format), and browser environments with WebVR and javascript libraries such as three.js or A-Frame.

Transmission usually has several meanings is used to dynamically render and update 3D objects and scenes. With such a definition volumetric data transmission system can be seen in the following areas:

- General users with no specific product: Google (maps, draco), Adobe, Facebook (Lego3D, Oculus), Nokia.
- Companies including such technologies in their current or future product line: Apple (ToF captor in 2020 iPadPro), Microsoft (Minecraft, babylon.js, Paint3D, Remix3D, Office), Autodesk (3ds Max)
- Websites including local rendering of 3D data stored using an above described format: [Apple Watch 3 Series](https://www.apple.com/apple-watch-series-3/)⁴³
- Platforms for 3D animated objects: [Sketchfab](https://sketchfab.com/)⁴⁴, [Cesium](https://cesium.com/index.html)⁴⁵, ...
- Video game technologies: [COLLADA](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COLLADA)⁴⁶, [OpenGEX](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_Game_Engine_Exchange)⁴⁷

⁴³<https://www.apple.com/apple-watch-series-3/>

⁴⁴ <https://sketchfab.com/>

⁴⁵ <https://cesium.com/index.html>

⁴⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/COLLADA>

⁴⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_Game_Engine_Exchange

3.3.4. Holographic communication systems

Immersive experiences are increasing their popularity, creating new use-cases and technologies as volumetric video, considered the best way to represent photographic natural content in 3D. The video technology sector is focusing on real-time representations to transmit humans' holographic representations in three-dimensional conferencing systems, as Microsoft's real-time holoportation [12], involving high volumes of data and creating new needs in the videoconferencing field.

In bi-dimensional conferencing, communications are handled by multipoint servers, connecting participants, providing parallelization, multi-distribution, adaptability, transcoding and multi-resolution. Multipoint Control Units (MCU) [13], as used in WebRTC services, are devices implementing the above features. Given the early stage of the holoportation development, there is huge interest in introducing similar concepts for volumetric video. With the demanding volumetric video needs, cloud processing promises an enhanced user experience, providing high quality also when an expensive hardware is not available. According to the MPEG vision, summarized in the Network Based Media Processing (NBMP)⁴⁸ paper, the computational load of Augmented/Virtual/Extended Reality clients can be reduced moving out of the end-device the heaviest part of the processing. Considering the variety, and the big amount, of information to be handled in this three-dimensional, and multimedia, environment, and considering the different characteristics that this kind of video has, compared to the traditional 2D video, it will be important to have a component able to process, merge and tune the content in order to have this delivered in the best possible way depending on the end-user client characteristics.

Such solution can be exploited for:

- Videoconferencing next generation solutions, in line with the work of companies such as Skype, Google, Zoom, among others.
- Telecommunication managing systems, as Cisco's Unified Communication System (UCS)⁴⁹.
- Network providers, exploiting the cloud nature and the virtualization possibilities of the system.
- Gaming industry, including the players' holograms substituting avatars for online multiplayer sessions.

⁴⁸ Motion Picture Experts Group, «NBMP Vision Paper,» [Online]. Available: <https://mpeg.chiariglione.org/standards/mpeg-i/network-based-media-processing/nbmp-vision-paper>.

⁴⁹ Gai et al, Cisco Unified Computing System (UCS): A Complete Reference Guide to the Cisco Data Center Virtualization Server Architecture, 2010

4. IDENTIFIED STAKEHOLDERS / PARTNERS / ACTORS

4.1. Introduction

As previously mentioned in section 2, there are multiple fields of application of AR/VR technologies. Since the birth of VRtogether, a clear common aim was outlined regardless of the intended end-use case: to develop and deliver a first-in-class Social VR platform to the market.

Inherently, social VR encompasses multiple applications, end-users and potential VR experiences. It is important then, in a market-wise manner, to analyse the current status of Social VR, the available platforms and solutions. Being able to have a panoramic overview of the market, together with the developed technology will enable to pinpoint the enabled market uses and end-users to target.

Serving this purpose, a first good comparison of 16 social VR platforms is available from Ryan Schultz⁵⁰ website:

Name/ Company	Purpose of Platform	Desktop (Non-VR) OS Support	VR Headset Support	Avatars Can Freely Move Around?	Default Avatars	Architecture/ Game Engine	Open Source or Closed Source?
AltspaceVR Microsoft	General Purpose	Windows	Oculus Rift, Quest, Go, HTC Vive, Valve Index, Windows MR, Gear VR, Google Daydream Mobile: Android	Yes	Cartoon-Like Avatars	Unity	Closed Source
Anyland	General Purpose	None	Oculus Rift, HTC Valve, Valve Index, Windows MR No mobile support	Yes	A Pair of Hands (You Build Your Own Avatar)	Unity	Closed Source
Bigsreen, Inc.	Media Consumption (Video, TV, Movies)	Windows	Oculus Rift, Quest, Go, HTC Vive, Valve Index, Windows MR, Gear VR No mobile support	Yes / No	Cartoon-Like Avatars	Unity	Closed Source
Cryptovoxels Nolan Consulting Ltd.	General Purpose	Windows, MacOS, Linux (Web Based)	Any that support WebVR: Oculus Rift, Quest, Go, HTC Vive, Valve Index, Windows MR, Gear VR, Google Daydream Mobile: iOS and Android	Yes	Artist Mannequin Avatar (Not Changeable)	BabylonJS	Closed Source
Engage VR Education Holdings PLC	Education	Windows	Oculus Rift, Oculus Quest (via SideQuest), HTC Vive, Valve Index, Windows MR No mobile support	Yes	Human Avatars	Unity	Closed Source
High Fidelity	Business/Remote Workteams (Formerly General Purpose)	Windows, MacOS	Oculus Rift, HTC Vive, Valve Index, Windows MR Mobile: Android support	Yes	Artist Mannequin Avatar	QT-C++	Open Source
JanusVR	General Purpose	Windows, MacOS, Linux	Any that support WebVR: Oculus Rift, Oculus Go, HTC Vive, Valve Index, Windows MR, Gear VR, Google Daydream Mobile: iOS and Android	Yes	Artist Mannequin Avatars	QT-C++	Closed Source
Mozilla Hubs Mozilla	General Purpose	Windows, MacOS, Linux (Web Based)	Any that support WebVR: Oculus Rift, Oculus Go, HTC Vive, Valve Index, Windows MR, Gear VR, Google Daydream Mobile: iOS and Android	Yes	Cartoon-Like Avatars	ThreeJS + Aframe (AmmoJS for Physics)	Open Source
NeosVR Solirax Ltd	General Purpose	None	Oculus Rift, HTC Vive, Valve Index, Windows MR (Oculus Quest and Oculus Go in beta test for Patreon)	Yes	Cartoon or Human Avatars	Unity	Closed Source

⁵⁰ Social VR Platform comparison: <https://ryanschultz.com/2019/11/12/an-updated-comparison-chart-of-sixteen-social-vr-platforms-first-draft-november-2019/>

			supporters only) Mobile: Android (beta for Patreon supporters only)				
Rec Room Against Gravity	Games	Windows	Oculus Rift, Oculus Quest, HTC Vive, Valve Index, Windows MR, PSVR Mobile : IOS	Yes	Cartoon-Like Avatars	Unity	Closed Source
Sansar Linden Lab	General Purpose (New Focus on Live Events)	Windows	Oculus Rift, HTC Vive, Windows MR (unofficial)	Yes	Human Avatars	Custom, Proprietar y	Closed Source
Sinespace Sine Wave Entertainm ent	General Purpose	Windows, MacOS, Linux (also a Web Client)	Oculus Rift, HTC Vive Mobile: IOS and Android	Yes	Human Avatars	Unity	Closed Source
Somnium Space	General Purpose	Windows	Oculus Rift, HTC Vive, Valve Index, Windows MR, Gear VR, Google Daydream	Yes	Head-and- Shoulders Avatars (Full- Body Avatars are Planned)	Unity	Closed Source
VRChat VRChat Inc.	General Purpose	Windows	Oculus Rift, Oculus Quest, HTC Vive, Valve Index, Windows MR	Yes	Cartoon or Human Avatars (You Can Select a New Avatar In-World or Create a Custom Avatar Using the Tafi Beta App)	Unity	Closed Source
vTime XR vTime Limited	Chat	Windows	Oculus Rift, Go, Windows MR, Gear VR, Google Daydream Mobile: IOS and Android	No, Locked to Seat	Human Avatars		Closed Source
Wave WaveVR	Music Performance	Windows	Oculus Rift, HTC Vive, Valve Index, Windows MR	Yes	Cartoon-Like Avatars	Unity	Closed Source

Table 6 - Social VR Platform comparison

4.2. VR Together Applications and End-Use Cases

The VR Together consortium, when working towards common pilots, have been developing multiple technology components and even 2 platforms, which can be used for a broad spectrum of Social VR uses. Based on the capabilities of the VR Together components and the platforms and the experience and focus of the partners, **3 use cases have been clearly identified** as promising and viable for market use:

1. **VR Conferencing**, where the focus is placed on the communication and collaboration between multiple users of the system. The users can see each-other, talk to each-other and sometimes also interact with objects in a virtual world. This end-use case aims to cater both VR audiences, consumer and enterprise & public sector.
2. **Social VR for Broadcasters and Operators**
3. **Interactive simulation**

In the following chapters the existing platforms and market players are analysed.

4.3. VR Conferencing systems

4.3.1. Platforms for residential user

Already at the beginning of this century and even before that in 1994, Worlds.com launched a Virtual World with communities and avatars to chat and interact, Second Life by Linden Lab was a Virtual World where users (“residents”) represented by an avatar could interact with objects and other residents. This virtual world was completely 3D, but client software could only present 2D graphics.

With the availability of affordable VR headsets, real 3D immersive experiences with multiple users became possible. Also Linden Lab launched with a new world: Sansar. In Sansar, users can create a 3D world, where they can share interactive virtual experiences, including conversations in VR. The representation of each user is still using a graphical avatar. Other features like buying and selling of virtual goods, are identical to the features in Second Life.

Some platforms focus on the shared experience, for instance watching an event or a movie together (see also next chapter VR for Broadcaster).

Examples of VR platforms for social interaction⁵¹:

4.3.1.1. Linden Lab / Sansar

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue
2017	San Francisco	101-500	Consumer	For Sale
Linden Lab received funding from Jeff Bezos.				

Available for: Oculus Rift, HTC Vive, desktop

Sansar is a social virtual reality platform developed and owned by the San Francisco-based firm Linden Lab and launched to the general public on July 31, 2017. The platform enables user-created 3D spaces where people can create and share interactive social experiences, such as playing games, watching videos, and having conversations in VR. Each participant is represented by a detailed avatar that is the graphical representation of the user including speech-driven facial animations and motion-driven body animations. The service was free to use, with advanced features available for paying subscribers.

In February 2020⁵², after less than two years of operation, Linden Labs is stopping its VR social platform and refocusing back to Second-Life products on desktop. Sansar has been unable to gain enough traction to be sustainable. No official deal has been announced yet, but the company is in talks with potential buyers.

⁵¹ All company summary profiles from [Crunchbase](#), [Owler](#) and [Dealroom](#), information on specific platforms from <https://medium.com/immersively/vr-for-virtual-meetings-the-ultimate-guide-d0c9ebe634d4> and [Ryan Schultz pages](#).

⁵² <https://www.roadtovr.com/sansar-spin-off-linden-lab-refocus-second-life/>

4.3.1.1. AltspaceVR⁵³

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue
2013	Redwood City	10-50	Consumer	N/A
AltspaceVR was acquired by Microsoft in October 2017, after an earlier announcement in July 2017 to close down business.				

Available for: Go, Quest, Rift, Steam, flat desktop

Altspace is one of the oldest VR meeting apps. On the one hand, you can use it to meet friends in private rooms where only you hear what is being said, but you can also go exploring in rooms and environments to meet others. You can play board games, draw, watch a stand-up show, sing karaoke and a variety of other activities.

Figure 26 – ALTSPACE VR Experience

When you start Altspace you end up in a lobby which is a common space for everyone. Then you can either create a private room and invite others, or visit any of the activities available. You can also see a schedule of upcoming group activities — you could say that the focus of Altspace is to gather groups for specific events. There have been live concerts, weddings, game nights, meditation sessions, language lessons and lots of other things⁵⁴.

Because of a slow market take-up and because most hardware did not yet support the features like eye-tracking, AltSpaceVR could not survive independently, so they were acquired by Microsoft.

⁵³ <https://altvr.com/>

⁵⁴ <https://immersive.ly/vr-for-virtual-meetings-ultimate-guide/>

4.3.1.2. Mozilla Hubs⁵⁵

Available for: Almost Everything

Mozilla, the company behind Firefox, is of great importance for the development of the common webXR protocols that are being put in place — and thus the building blocks of the 3-dimensional internet that we will live in through VR and AR. Hubs is Mozilla’s social VR platform and is very simple and spartan in design. It is built using open source tools like WebVR and A-Frame (same technologies as used for the web based VR Together platform).

Figure 27 – Mozilla Hubs experiment

Through their web tool “Spoke”, you have the opportunity to easily create and insert your own 3D models of environments and objects and meet others. Hubs are accessed through the browser in your VR headset and even works with Cardboard VR glasses — or in flat mode on your normal browser.

4.3.1.3. RecRoom⁵⁶

Rec Room is a product from Against Gravity, is cross-platform, free, and can be played with or without a VR headset. Focus is on hanging-out in player-created rooms or build your own rooms with friends. With hundreds of rooms being added daily, you'll never run out of things to do!

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue
2016	Seattle	51-100	Consumer	

⁵⁵ <https://hubs.mozilla.com/#/>

⁵⁶ <https://rec.net/>

Rec Room has raised a total of \$29M in funding, with a latest round on June, 12 2019 of \$24M.

Available for: Quest, PCVR, PSVR, iPad

When you start Rec Room you can choose from a few simple avatars, clothes and hairstyles. Just like most other social games, it's easy to pick up and use directly without a manual. Rec Room is not a game that you need to plug strategy or button combinations into, just jump in and see what happens.⁵⁷

Figure 28 – RecRoom environment

In the game that can almost be described as a social sandbox, it is late play and fun that applies. You can play paintball, dodgeball, charades, and Frisbee golf, or just hang out with others in the social rooms.

Over time, Rec Room has also received powerful creator tools and there are millions of user-built rooms and worlds to explore.

4.3.1.4. VRChat⁵⁸

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue
2014	San Francisco	1010	Consumer	

VRChat has raised a total of \$15.2M in funding over 3 rounds. Their latest funding was raised on Sep 5, 2019 from a Series C round. (HTC injected funds in 2016 and 2019)

⁵⁷ <https://immersive.ly/vr-for-virtual-meetings-ultimate-guide/>

⁵⁸ <https://www.vrchat.com/>

Available for: Oculus Quest, Oculus Rift, SteamVR, Viveport. Supports cross-play between Quest, PC Desktop and PC VR

VRChat is an ever-expanding virtual universe powered by the community who creates and shares virtual worlds, avatars, and interactive experiences.

Figure 29 - VRChat available on Steam platform

Since its founding in 2015, the platform has grown to millions of users and features a community of creators who have published tens of millions of unique pieces of content.

Using Unity and the VRChat SDK, creators can build avatars or worlds and upload them to share with others.

4.3.1.5. PlutoVR⁵⁹

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue
2015	Seattle	11-50	Consumer, enterprise	
Pluto VR has raised a total of \$13.9M in funding over 1 round. This was a Series A round raised on Apr 13, 2017.				

Available for: HTC VIVE, Windows MR, Oculus Rift, as an alpha release

Pluto is a spatial computing communication service. It creates the illusion of face-to-face presence, fostering a unique intimacy that he hopes will take virtual communication to a new level. The system allows the user create its own avatar, control the opacity of each person, mute mics or make “calls” to other people without needing an avatar, and more.

⁵⁹ <https://www.plutovr.com/>

Pluto’s CEO said the company has no immediate plans to release its product more broadly, and that Pluto VR is focused on getting the little things right with alpha customers and rolling out slowly.

Figure 30- Pluto VR lets you talk to other people within virtual reality apps.

4.3.1.6. vTime (both VR and AR)

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue
2013	Liverpool	11-50	Consumer	\$<1M
vTime Limited has raised a total of \$7.6M in funding over 1 round. This was a Series A round raised on Apr 11, 2018.				

Available for: cardboard, oculus go, oculus quest, steam, oculus PC, mobile AR

In vTime you can have meetings with up to three other people at the same time. You can choose from around 20 different environments, ranging from campfires to spaceships and on the seafloor. The idea behind vTime is very simple but works well. You choose rooms and who you want to talk to, then you are all transported to a place where you all sit down and look at each other. In vTime you sit in a stationary position and the conversation is in focus. For meetings with small groups, it is a convenient alternative for social VR as it’s available on many platforms. In addition, the environments and avatars are very well modelled. It is also possible to upload your own 360 pictures and use them as environments.

Figure 31 - vTime Snapshot

vTime is built with JanusXR, the open source platform that continued after Janus VR was discontinued and dissolved.

4.3.1.7. Facebook Horizon

Facebook Horizon is the follow-up of Facebook Spaces and Oculus Rooms.

Available for: Quest, Rift

After some first social VR experiments from Facebook / Oculus, their new platform Horizon is underway in 2020. It looks like a kind of “Second Life meets Pixar” world where you will be able to jump into many social activities and mini-games together.

Figure 32 - Facebook Horizon

Facebook Horizon will allow users to design their own diverse avatars and hop between virtual locales through portals called Telepods, watch movies and consume other media with friends and play multiplayer games together, like Wing Strikers. It also will include human guides, known as Horizon Locals, who can give users assistance and protect their safety in the VR world so trolls can't run rampant.

4.3.1.8. Others

- Cluster is a Tokyo based start-up, providing a platform where participants can virtually participate in an event by wearing a headset and communicating with each other.
- Discontinued platforms:
 - VReal
 - High Fidelity
 - PixVana / SPIN studio
 - Oculus Rooms and Facebook Spaces, to be replaced by Facebook Horizon
 - Sansar

4.3.2. Platforms for business/corporate users

Real-time communication in a business environment has of course evolved from classic telephony to video conferencing. Video conferencing or video telephony has been started as early as the 19th century, but it became only a commodity when the needed bandwidth, CPU resources and codecs were affordable and widely available.

In a corporate environment, with dedicated video conferencing rooms, setups have been created to make the experience as real as face-to-face meetings. E.g. Cisco's telepresence rooms with identical setups in the near and far-end give quickly the impression everyone is sitting around the same table in the same room.

These setups are very expensive, fixed and most of the time reserved for higher management use and board meetings.

Some start-ups (like Mimesys and Spatial) have seen the opportunity to build VR conferencing and collaboration platforms for corporate use. Instead of the inclusion of movie players or event podia, these platforms add document presentation, (real) object representation and interaction and of course communication. They are all avatar based, with some working on life-like avatars, following gestures (tracking controller movement) and facial expressions (using camera).

Mimesys from Belgium has taken a different approach, working with real-time capture of the users with 3D cameras and representing them as photorealistic "holograms" in VR or AR. Their platform resembles the most to VR Together's platform. Last year they were bought by Magic Leap.

4.3.2.1. MeetinVR⁶⁰

MeetinVR provide an avatar based solution for enterprise meetings in Virtual Reality. The solution combines the flexibility of online meetings with the interactivity of in-person meetings, enabling companies to collaborate inside virtual work-spaces designed to promote engagement and productivity. It has well-designed virtual meeting spaces for groups up to 7-8 people, as well as an auditorium for bigger group presentations. Participants can easily bring up notes, browser screens and scribble in 2D or 3D to communicate concepts and ideas.

⁶⁰ <https://meetinvr.net/>

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue
2016	Copenhagen	+/- 10	Enterprises	<1M
Private company.				

Available for: PCVR, Quest

Figure 33 – MeetinVR snapshot

4.3.2.2. Doghead Simulations / Rumii⁶¹

Doghead simulation proposes a social-virtual reality space, called Rumii, that enables people to collaborate and communicate in one room from anywhere in the world - as though they're all in the same physical location. Step into your virtual reality office or classroom. Rumii can be used across virtual reality headsets and desktops for collaboration, classes and meetings. Great for remote teams, education and digital nomads. To enable a truly immersive experience, Rumi is loaded with features that address all the communication and collaboration needs.

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue
2016	Seattle	+/- 10	Collaboration, Education, Enterprise Software	<1M
Private company.				

⁶¹ <https://www.dogheadsimulations.com/>

Figure 34 - Doghead Simulations

Theoretically the solution supports up to 40 users per room depending on devices capabilities. Generally

4.3.2.3. Spatial⁶²

Spatial designs and develops an augmented reality collaboration platform that provides holographic teleportation solutions for enterprises.

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue
2016	New-York	+/- 10	Enterprises	N/A
Spatial has raised a total of \$22.3M in funding over 5 rounds. Their latest funding was raised on Jan 30, 2020 from a Series A round				

⁶² <https://spatial.io/>

Figure 35 - Spatial AR collaboration system

Spatial with its partners Nreal, a mixed reality headset manufacturer, and Qualcomm Technologies, are together joining forces with South Korean cellular carrier LG Uplus, Japanese telecommunications operator KDDI, and German telecommunications company Deutsche Telekom respectively, to work towards the acceleration of mass market adoption of AR collaboration systems.

4.3.2.4. Magic Leap / Mimesys

Magic Leap is a proprietary wearable technology that enables users to interact with digital devices in a completely visually cinematic way. Their AR headset combines a user's inherent visual ability with mobile computing – giving visual output equivalent to real-world experience but powered by mobile tech. using their Dynamic Digitized Lightfield Signal, they generate images indistinguishable from real objects and place those images seamlessly into the real world.

In May 2019 Magic Leap announced that they've agreed to acquire Mimesys⁶³, a Belgian start up that provides volumetric video systems similar to VR Together capture systems. After starting to work in the VR ecosystem they decided to pivot to the AR ecosystem.

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue
2010	Miami	+1000	Platform for development of apps, games and movies	\$180M

Magic Leap has raised a total of \$2.6B in funding over 8 rounds. Their latest funding was raised on Dec 7, 2019 from a Series E round.

Despite significant fundraising, Magic Leap seems to be struggling to maintain a viable business model. According to media⁶⁴ the company is for sale for 10 billion \$ and would not find interested investors

⁶³ <https://www.wearable-technologies.com/2019/05/magic-leap-buys-ar-telepresence-startup-mimesys-to-boost-spatial-computing-offerings/>

4.3.2.5. Glue Collaboration⁶⁵

Glue is a modern collaboration platform that takes advantage of recent advances in immersive 3D graphics, virtual reality, and cloud computing. It is intended for business professionals who need global remote access to a shared team space for efficient collaboration. Representation of users is done through avatars.

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue (Estimated)
2017	Helsinki	30	Enterprise	
Glue Collaboration has raised a total of €3.5M in funding over 2 rounds. Their latest funding was raised on Nov 14, 2019 from a Seed round.				

They are selling their solution and support via monthly licenses per user :

- up to 10 users - 500€
- 11 to 100 users - 150€ + 45 € per user
- 100+ users - 150€ + 40 € per user

Figure 36 - Glue collaborative solution

4.3.2.6. WorldViz⁶⁶

WorldViz develops and provides VR software and platform that offers three-dimensional visualization solutions for businesses and enterprises. Since 2012, the company has been recognized for their expertise in VR solutions, they were providing guidance to researchers,

⁶⁴ <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-magic-leap-m-a/augmented-reality-company-magic-leap-to-explore-sale-bloomberg-idUSKBN20Y3LS>

⁶⁵ <https://glue.work/>

⁶⁶ <https://www.worldviz.com/>

trainers, teachers, government leaders, and business teams all around the globe. More recently they have focused on creating VR creation and collaboration tools that are accessible to non-technical users.

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue (Estimated)
2002	Santa Barbara	45	Enterprise	\$6M
WorldViz has raised a total of \$5.8M in funding over 3 rounds. Their latest funding was raised on Jun 22, 2018 from a Series A round.				

WorldViz product line includes different solutions:

- “VizMove Showrooms” for interactive, scalable VR projection solutions,

Figure 37 - VizMove - Georgia State University, Suffolk Construction's Smart Lab

- VizBox delivers fully immersive 6DOF VR content. Easy set-up, self-contained, and robust enough for safe shipping and travel

Figure 38 - Worldviz - VizBox portable solution

- VR Motion Tracking systems
- Vizard VR Eye Tracking Features
- VR Immersive training software

4.3.2.7. VirBELA

VirBELA is a provider of virtual reality platforms that allows users to connect with avatars, voice and text chat and embedded learning simulations and games. They are providing their solution to large companies or universities and claim to be able to support online conferences of any size and format.

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue (Estimated)
2012	Washington	+/-20	Enterprise	\$4M
In October 2018, VirBELA was acquired by eXp World Holdings, a residential real estate broker, for an undisclosed amount				

Figure 39- VirBELA Team meeting system

4.3.2.8. Others actors

- meetingRoom⁶⁷ is another business-oriented social VR platform, by an Irish company, with support for Windows, Mac, iOS, and Android devices, as well as Oculus Rift, HTC Vive, and Windows Mixed Reality (WMR) headsets.
- InsiteVR⁶⁸ or The Wild⁶⁹ are actors providing immersive collaborative systems for Architecture, Engineering, and Construction
- Telia VR Conferencing is a platform developed by Mixrive⁷⁰ and provided by the Finnish telecommunications operator Telia,

4.4. Social VR for Broadcasters and operators

As with many other technologies, the ability to be part of a group using VR will be essential to make VR be a success for the Broadcaster and operators market. While most VR experiences are currently single-user, there have been developments promoting social experiences, actors

⁶⁷ <https://meetingroom.io/>

⁶⁸ <https://www.insitevr.com/>

⁶⁹ <https://thewild.com/>

⁷⁰ <https://www.mixtive.com/vrconference>

like Livelike for live sports events or CineVR with its Social VR movie theatre app, propose new multi-user content consumption platform. We expect that user engagement with VR will be much greater.

In November 2019, SK Telecom, in South Korea, created its own interactive 5G universe, 'Virtual Social World'. Many carriers are talking up VR gaming as a 5G use case. SK Telecom has launched an entire VR gaming ecosystem and partnership platform, to accelerate usage of its Jump VR app and services. SK Telecom is one of the most progressive operators in VR and AR service development. In the meantime, O2 in the UK has created an unusual partnership offer with MelodyVR, it allows O2 customers subscribing to the new 5G services to have free access to a 12-month subscription to the live virtual reality (VR) music performance platform.

All this market dynamism surrounding VR as a 5G use case exemplifies the market potential of the VR Together's project.

4.4.1. MelodyVR⁷¹

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue (Estimated)
2015	London	+/- 80	Sports, Video Streaming, Virtual Reality	+/- \$15M
MelodyVR has raised a total of \$60M in funding over 1 round. This was a Venture - Series Unknown round raised on May 22, 2019.				

4.4.1.1. General description

MelodyVR is a Virtual Reality music platform available in the US, UK and Europe. They are the only licensed VR music platform in the world and have secured partnerships with all the major record labels -Universal Music Group, Sony Music Entertainment Warner Music Group as well as Jay Z's Roc Nation and many more.

4.4.1.2. Business Model

The company's end-to-end process has helped some of the world's biggest artists take their first steps into virtual reality. They boast the world's largest library of interactive music content, having worked with over 650 international artists to date. Users can have multiple perspectives- from deep in the crowd to up-close-and-personal with the band on stage. As well as recorded shows, the company will live stream concerts via Virtual Reality having partnered with a number of major UK venues. They are also planning to make its content available as Android and iOS apps, to widen its reach beyond the VR-headset market, as well as expanding its business model beyond a-la-carte sales to "platform advertising and sponsorship".

⁷¹ <https://melodyvr.com/>

4.4.2. LiveLike⁷²

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue (Estimated)
2014	New York	+/- 40	Sports, Video Streaming, Virtual Reality	+/- \$15M
Livelike has raised a total of \$14.7M in funding over 5 rounds. Their latest funding was raised on Aug 9, 2019				

4.4.2.1. General description

LiveLike is a next-gen OTT sports technology company delivering the live sports experience to sports fans. They have developed a broadcasting platform designed to enable global sports organizations to offer live immersive VR experience to their customers. For the consumer, this means that instead of sitting and watching a game or match on a phone or television, the entire stadium experience can be brought to their home. To improve immersivity, LiveLike reinvents the user experience around four pillars: social, interactivity, content and immersivity.

Figure 40- FoxSport VR social teaser - Powered by LiveLike

4.4.2.2. Key Customers

LiveLike's key clients and events include: Fox Sports VR, French Open, UEFA Champions League, Manchester City, BT, France Television, Sky Germany, NASCAR, Super Bowl LI, Huawei, and many more.

⁷² <https://www.livelikevr.com/>

4.4.3. BigScreen⁷³

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue (Estimated)
2014	San Francisco Bay Area	+/- 40	Sports, Video Streaming, Virtual Reality	+/- \$15M

Bigscreen has raised a total of \$14M in funding over 2 rounds. Their latest funding was raised on Oct 10, 2017 from a Series A round

4.4.3.1. General description

Bigscreen is a start-up creating an immersive virtual reality telepresence platform that aims to revolutionize the way people work, play, hangout, and collaborate. Use cases of Bigscreen include both entertainment and productivity. It's used as a virtual living room to watch movies, play video games, browse the web, and hangout with friends. It's also used for productivity as a tool for remote teams to collaborate together in virtual offices.

Since the beta launch in March 2016, Bigscreen has become one of the most popular and highest rated VR apps on the Oculus Store. Power users spend 20-30 hours per week in Bigscreen, making it one of the most widely used apps in the industry.

The first application of Bigscreen VR app lets users mirror their desktop monitor in virtual reality, and share it with friends. In 2018 Bigscreen has received a new update which adds three new "Big Room" environments which support up to 12 players simultaneously.

Figure 41- Image courtesy Bigscreen

⁷³ <https://www.bigscreenvr.com/cinema>

4.4.3.2. Key Customers / Partners

In December 2019, Bigscreen and Paramount Pictures announced a multi-year agreement to distribute classic 2D & 3D films in 10 countries worldwide through Bigscreen, the social VR movie watching platform⁷⁴.

4.4.3.3. Business Model

Bigscreen is available for free with cross-platform support on all leading VR headsets, including the Oculus Quest, Oculus Go, Oculus Rift S, Samsung GearVR, Valve Index, HP Reverb, and more. All SteamVR and Windows Mixed Reality headsets are supported.

Bigscreen Cinema featuring Paramount Pictures movies is available in the U.S., UK, Germany, Canada, Japan, France, Australia, Netherlands, Sweden, and Spain.

Virtual tickets for watching a movie start at \$3.99 and vary depending on the movie and country.

4.4.3.4. Competitor

Skybox VR⁷⁵ is a VR video player developed by Source Technology⁷⁶ (UK) that provide environment like Bigscreen but without the social element. It offers a bunch of different cinemas and environments for you to watch content in. It is possible to load files that are stored locally on a Quest HMD or stream content from a DLNA Home server.

4.4.4. NextVR⁷⁷

NextVR is a virtual reality platform that provides live streaming videos for sports, events, concerts and cinematic productions. In 2018 they announced a partnership with Oculus Venues to allow people to watch live concerts, sports, comedy shows and more along with friends and thousands of other people in VR. It combines live social engagement through avatars and NextVR's VR content for an immersive event experience.

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue (Estimated)
2016	Laguna Beach, California	+/- 30	Sports, Video Streaming, Virtual Reality	+/- \$8M
NextVR has raised a total of \$115.5M in funding over 3 rounds. Their latest funding was raised on Aug 9, 2016 from a Series B round.				

⁷⁴ <https://www.prnewswire.co.uk/news-releases/bigscreen-and-paramount-pictures-sign-multi-year-agreement-to-distribute-movies-in-virtual-reality-873413300.html>

⁷⁵ <https://skybox.xyz/en/>

⁷⁶ <https://www.source-technology.com/>

⁷⁷ <https://nextvr.com/>

4.4.4.1. Business Model

Currently most of the channels produced by NextVR, are delivered for free and are sponsored by events organisations (NHRA⁷⁸, UEFA⁷⁹, Wimbledon, Moscow Ballet's, ...).

They are also providing Live and On Demand access to various channels and sports events. One of their main products includes the delivery of NBA League access Live Streaming and in apps VR games. The VR option PASS is currently sold for \$49.99 compared to the classical NBA league PASS which is sold for 140€ to 170€ depending on the number of devices allowed to stream content.

4.5. Interactive simulation

The world of virtual reality is in a very different place than it was just a few short years ago. The shared experiences, between avatars so far, are creating significant opportunities and address a need in both the cultural and entertainment markets. Interactivity is a tool that enriches it technologically and conceptually. Other markets enter this world by having visualized its potential. Gaming, medicine, education and entertainment have opened the door to other worlds such as museums, heritage conservation, business teleconferencing, dating, etc.

The best and most interesting VR experiences are the ones that are impossible to experience outside of a fixed installation. Very interesting offers appear within the cultural world such as exhibitions, theatres, cultural centers where all realities – be they virtual, augmented or mixed, are woven together. One example is the Phi Centre's Theatre of Virtuality⁸⁰. The exhibition just wrapped its fourth phase (a six-month residency in Venice that ran parallel to the International Biennale Art). A similarly themed exhibition, called Cadavre Exquis⁸¹ was in Montreal in 2019. The Acute Art Foundation⁸² has also started to produce interesting interactive and immersive works by interesting and relevant artists.

In the coming years, immersive technology will allow museum exhibits and escape rooms to become gateways to other worlds. We also envision cutting-edge experience design to solve the issue of throughput that is plaguing the immersive industry. A well-designed installation or exhibit should have no wait times, but instead allow the audience to enter virtual worlds at their will.

The audience must feel as if they have been truly transported to another world and the characters they are interacting with must seem convincingly real.

Museum Thyssen Bornemisza developed in 2017 the "Enter into the Painting"⁸³ experience. The viewer could delve into 3 master works from the Thyssen collection, a Van Gogh, a Mondrian and a 17th century Dutch still life by Baltassar VAn der Ast. Walking through the French meadows of Vangogh's painting, hearing the birds and feeling the wind, generated a large influx of public. An initiative launched for the International Museum Day that has been traveling for 2 years throughout Spain.

Immersive experiences involve digital design and a process of using computer-generated images to design living spaces and create interaction with the public.

⁷⁸ National Hot Road Association

⁷⁹ European Football Association

⁸⁰ <https://phi-centre.com/en/>

⁸¹ <https://phi-centre.com/en/event/cadavreexquis-en/>

⁸² <https://acuteart.com>

⁸³ <https://www.museothyssen.org/en/support/corporate-support/enter-painting-virtual-reality-travelling>

More and more we attend a demanding public that needs hyperrealism, interaction, immersion, sensations and unique experiences. One that is more entertaining, that cultivates deeper understanding and that results in a far more emotional and memorable experience for audiences.

In addition to those cultural immersive experiences, the consortium is also looking closely at location-based experiments. The best examples of entertainment are detailed below.

4.5.1. Dreamscape Immersive⁸⁴

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue (Estimated)
2016	California, Culver City, United States	+/- 60	Entertainment	N/A
Dreamscape Immersive has raised a total of \$36.7M ⁸⁵ in funding over 3 rounds. Their latest funding was raised on Sep 26, 2017 from a Series B round.				

4.5.1.1. General description

Dreamscape Immersive is an American entertainment and technology company. It creates story-based full-roam virtual reality (VR) experiences which allow users to simultaneously explore a virtual 3D environment, seeing fully rendered avatars of one another.

Dreamscape Immersive's vision is to combine the emotional power of Hollywood storytelling, the visceral excitement of great theme-park rides, and extraordinary new VR technology to create stories and worlds that push the limits of virtual reality.

Dreamscape gives people the opportunity to step into a story and watch it unfold around them as they explore cinematic worlds, characters and creatures never before thought possible. And each Dreamscape adventure is a shared experience, embracing the human desire to explore, learn and enjoy together.

Figure 42- Dreamscape experience

⁸⁴ <https://dreamscapeimmersive.com/>

⁸⁵ https://www.crunchbase.com/search/funding_rounds/field/organizations/funding_total/dreamscape-immersive

4.5.1.2. Technical architecture of the service

Dreamscape Immersive offers multi-user Virtual Reality experiences for groups of up to 6-8 people depending on the experience. A real-time motion capture system captures the positions and orientations of active markers on the user's hands and feet, as well as on the VR headset and backpack PC. The real-time mocap data is used to animate full-body avatars - uniquely designed for each story - which can be selected by the users before they start their experience. Each experience is a shared multiplayer environment in which all participants can see each other, as well as talk to and interact with one another.

The experiences take place on a room-scale set, enabling users to move around untethered in the virtual environment. The rooms are augmented with a variety of haptic elements - tracked by the mocap system or placed in strategic locations - which can be interacted with or experienced. Further augmentations include such effects as wind, vibrations or even moisture and smells.

4.5.1.3. Business Model

Dreamscape Immersive uses a B2C model where clients come to a venue to take part in one or more of the experiences on offer. Each venue has multiple of the room-scale environments described before. Tickets are priced at \$20 per person.

Dreamscape Immersive at the time of writing exploits 4 locations; Los Angeles CA, Dallas TX and Columbus OH in the US as well as Dubai in the UAE.

4.5.2. The VOID⁸⁶

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue (Estimated)
2015	Lindon, Utah	+/- 100	Mixed reality entertainment	Unkown
The VOID has raised a total of \$20M in funding by James Murdoch, according to Bloomberg sources				

4.5.2.1. General description

THE VOID builds and operates virtual entertainment center that primarily focus on exploring immersive virtual worlds and dimensions with friends and family, and creating memorable experiences together. It specializes in creating 'hyper-reality' experiences that layer virtual reality over interactive real-world environments.

4.5.2.2. Technical Architecture of the service

The Void's mixed reality experiences utilize aspects of virtual reality, haptic feedback, and other physical effects; users wear a helmet with a head-mounted display, noise cancelling headphones and a hand tracking sensor, and a haptic suit containing 22 vibrators and a computer to power the headset.

⁸⁶ <https://www.thevoid.com/>

The system is designed to allow its users to freely walk through and explore a virtual world; in reality, the user is confined to a "stage" equipped with ceiling-mounted motion tracking cameras to read the user's movements.

To provide physical feedback, the "stage" contains foam walls, special effects equipment such as fans, mist machines, and heat lamps, as well as props representing items such as guns and torches; all of these physical elements correspond with elements within the virtual world seen through the headset, increasing the illusion of immersion

Figure 43- Guests suit up to explore another dimension at the Santa Monica outpost of The Void

Currently they have deployed their system mainly in the US market (12 spot), Canada (3), Malaysia and United Arab Emirates but they are planning to growth and extend their footprint in US (+5 spots) and Europe (Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Nederland, UK, Sweden)

4.5.2.3. Business Model

The VOID proposes to experiment VR immersive for groups of 4 people. Depending on the location you are able to choose which experience you want to select between titles like Jumanji, Avengers, Star Wars, RALPH BREAKS, Nicodemus or Ghostbusters.

The price for one session of 15 to 30 for 4 people is around 150\$.

4.5.3. Zero Latency⁸⁷

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue (Estimated)
2013	Melbourne, Australia	+100	Entertainment	A\$12 million

Zero Latency has raised a total of \$8.9M⁸⁸ in funding over 3 rounds. Their latest funding was raised on Dec 5, 2016 from a Series B round.

⁸⁷ <https://zerolatencyvr.com/>

⁸⁸ <https://www.crunchbase.com/organization/zero-latency>

Figure 44– Zero Latency players are shown with their tracked headset and controller

4.5.3.1. General description

Zero Latency develops free-roam virtual reality systems, primarily focused on VR gaming. The technology is intended to be used in location-based gaming spaces, or theme park attractions. In August 2015, Zero Latency opened the world’s first VR entertainment venue in North Melbourne, Australia.

4.5.3.2. Technical Architecture of the service

Zero Latency free-roam virtual reality gaming experiences allow users to move freely in an open space and not be constrained by cables and other immobile equipment. Depending on the venue, the play spaces range from 200 to 400 square meters. Their technology allows up to 8 players to share an experience simultaneously.

Players are equipped with a VR headset and backpack and supplied with a “controller”. The players are tracked using motion capture technology, which allows for the instant replication of their physical movements by their in-game avatars. A variety of haptic feedback techniques are used to increase immersion. To increase the perceptual scale of the environments the players move around in, Zero Latency exploits such concepts as change blindness redirection.

4.5.3.3. Business Model

Zero Latency both operates its own VR locations in a B2C model, as well as sells its system to other operators in different locations world-wide. At the time of writing Zero Latency has venues in 22 countries around the world. Tickets for a gaming session are sold at around \$35 per person depending on the location.

4.5.4. Nomadic VR⁸⁹

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue (Estimated)
2015	San Rafael, CA, USA	11-50	Entertainment	Unknown
Nomadic has raised a total of \$6.0M ⁹⁰ in funding over 2 rounds. Their latest funding was raised on Sep 7, 2018 from a Series A round.				

Figure 45– Nomadic VR players are shown with their tracked headset, VR backpack and prop

4.5.4.1. General description

Nomadic is a tactile, walkable virtual reality system that provides a game-like experience where you'll be able to physically engage with the virtual world around you. The company's first available attraction is a version of the VR shooter "Arizona Sunshine" that has been optimized for location-based entertainment.

4.5.4.2. Technical Architecture of the service

Nomadic operates using a free-roam VR solution on warehouse-scale stages in groups of up to 4 players. Users are equipped with a VR headset and backpack. Using Optitrack's motion capture system, the user's head position as well as the location of all props are tracked and reproduced in the virtual world.

Players can interact with physical props, including walls, doors, guns, elevators and trains. Key to Nomadic's approach is a modular stage that can easily be reconfigured to run additional experiences.

4.5.4.3. Business Model

Nomadic uses a B2C model where users come to a venue to play the experience on offer. They currently have a single location in Orlando, FL, USA. Tickets are priced at \$30, with a matinee pricing of \$25 for off hours

⁸⁹ <https://blurtheline.com/>

⁹⁰ <https://www.crunchbase.com/organization/nomadic-vr>

4.5.5. Hologate⁹¹

Creation	Headquarter	Company Size	Market	Revenue (Estimated)
2017	Munich, Germany	+/- 50	Simulation, virtual Reality	\$50M ⁹²

4.5.5.1. General description

HOLOGATE offers immersive media platforms for location-based entertainment and enterprise use. The system is an on-the-shelf solution that can be deployed in various locations (Hotel, Cruise Ship, Theme park, Escape room...). They have more than 300 active locations worldwide reaching more than 5 Million players per year.

4.5.5.2. Technical Architecture of the service

Minimal requirement to deploy the system is 5 x 5 m space and 2.8m height, 2x16 A power socket and 2Mbps internet connection.

Figure 46- Hologate Arena representation

4.5.5.3. Business Model

The Hologate Arena solution proposes multi genre gaming experience to address a wide range of market from Ages 6+ to 16+. According to Hologate commercial leaflet, average price for a session goes is around 7,5€ and can generate in average 12,5 K€ Monthly revenue⁹³.

⁹¹ <https://hologate.com/>

⁹² <https://www.forbes.com/sites/charliefink/2019/11/07/hologate-vr-serves-its-five-millionth-customer/#5d56f3b4427d>

⁹³ <http://hologate.com/info/>

5. STANDARDIZATION BODIES & TECHNOLOGIES

VR has been taken up by various Standardization Bodies (SDO's) and Industry Fora. From the start of the project, the partners have been actively participating in the work of MPEG, W3C, VQEG, 3GPP and VR-IF. Other groups working on VR like DVB, Khronos and VRARA are monitored.

Participating in those standardization groups is an opportunity for VRTogether to have a better exposure for the project, and to help spreading VR by making technologies more accessible for everyone.

5.1. 3GPP

The 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) covers cellular telecommunications network technologies, including radio access, the core transport network, and service capabilities - including work on codecs, security, and quality of service - and thus provides complete system specifications. The specifications also provide hooks for non-radio access to the core network, and for interworking with Wi-Fi networks.

In 3GPP SA1 (service requirements), VR aspects are addressed under efficient content delivery and low latency and high reliability and cover requirements on the data rates, motion-to-sound and motion-to-photon latencies, and audio/video synchronization.

3GPP SA4 (codecs) conducted a study from April 2016 to June 2017 on (360-3DOF) VR. The image below provides a summary of the study results. This work was adopted by ETSI and resulted in the technical report [TR126 918](#).

Figure 47 - 3GPP Technical report TR26.918

Following on the technical report TR126 918, 3GPP SA4 (codecs) conducted a study from July 2018 to March 2020 on 5G eXtended Reality services (5GXR). In this study 22 XR use cases were presented and discussed of which 16 are connected to conversational aspects. The study resulted in TR26.928.

Currently the work with closest relevance to VRTogether in the work item on 360 conferencing (Support of Immersive Teleconferencing and Telepresence for Remote Terminals, ITT4RT), which has started in Dec 2018. The main aim of this work is: "expected to enable scenarios with two-way audio and one-way immersive video, e.g., a remote single user wearing an HMD

participates to a conference will send audio and optionally 2D video (e.g., of a presentation, screen sharing and/or a capture of the user itself), but receives stereo or immersive voice/audio and immersive video captured by an omnidirectional camera in a conference room connected to a fixed network.” The WID will make changes to support the proposed functionality to TS 26.114 and TS 26.223.

The current timeline of the next normative work in 3GPP (Release 17) is shown in Figure 47

Figure 48 - 3GPP Timeplan for release 17

5.2. DVB

Digital Video Broadcasting (DVB) is an industry-led consortium of the world’s leading digital TV and technology companies, such as manufacturers, software developers, network operators, broadcasters and regulators, committed to designing open technical standards for the delivery of digital TV and other broadcast services. Standardization work is only undertaken after rigorous requirement setting in the Commercial Modules (CM).

After a study mission on VR in 2016⁹⁴, DVB started work on requirements in DVB CM-VR, however at the DVB Steering Board meeting in Geneva on 5 July 2018 it was decided, due to lack of contribution and redundancy work done by other fora like VR-IF, to pause work on VR.

5.3. Khronos: OpenXR API

The Khronos Group members are dedicated to the creation of royalty-free open standards for graphics, parallel computing, vision processing, and dynamic media on a wide variety of platforms. The OpenXR working group – previously known as the Khronos VR Initiative - is creating an open and royalty-free standard for VR and AR applications and devices.

OpenXR’s aim is to create a cross-platform VR standard that eliminates industry fragmentation.

⁹⁴ DVB Study Mission on Virtual Reality [online]. (published October, 2016) Available on: https://www.dvb.org/resources/public/whitepapers/dvb_vr_study_mission_report_summary.pdf

Figure 49 - OpenXR Interface Specification plan

The OpenXR forum promises to get a lot of industry support for their specification, from Microsoft, Oculus, Epic Games (Unreal), Unity and others.

5.4. W3C: WebXR API

The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) is an international community working to develop Web standards. The Immersive Web Working Group at W3C helps to bring high-performance Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) to the open Web via APIs to interact with XR devices and sensors in browsers.

The Immersive Web Working Group will develop standardized APIs to provide access to input and output capabilities commonly associated with XR hardware such as Google's Daydream, the Oculus Rift, the Samsung GearVR, the HTC Vive, and Windows Mixed Reality headsets and sensors as well as mobile handheld devices and standalone headsets such as the Oculus Go. The WG will develop APIs to enable the creation of XR web experiences that are embeddable in the Web of today, enabling progressive enhancement of existing sites.

The scope of the Immersive Web Working Group charter is to define APIs which:

- Detect available XR devices and sensors.
- Query XR devices for device-specific capabilities.
- Receive updated information about the device's position and orientation over time.
- Receive updated information about the device's environment.
- Present imagery to the device at the device's native frame rate, using the device's position and orientation over time to provide an immersive experience.
- Provide information about XR-specific input, including tracked controller state and hand gesture.

- For augmenting reality on devices which support AR, enable XR sessions that provide real-world display, and provide the ability to hit-test surfaces in the real world.

5.5. OpenXR vs WebXR API

Khronos' OpenXR API does cover the same basic capabilities as the WebXR Device API for native applications. As such it may seem like WebXR and OpenXR have a relationship like WebGL and OpenGL, where the web API is a near 1:1 mapping of the native API. This is not the case with WebXR and OpenXR, as they are distinct APIs being developed by different standards bodies.

That said, given the shared subject matter many of the same concepts are represented by both APIs in different ways and one can expect that once OpenXR becomes publicly available it will be reasonable to implement WebXR's feature set using OpenXR as one of multiple possible native backends.

5.6. MPEG

The Moving Picture Experts Group (MPEG) is a working group of ISO/IEC with the mission to develop standards for coded representation of digital audio and video and related data.

Since mid-2017, MPEG started working on MPEG Immersive (MPEG-I). MPEG-I targets future immersive applications. The goal of this new standard is to enable various forms of audio-visual immersion, including panoramic video with 2D and 3D audio, with various degrees of true 3D visual perception (leaning toward 6 degrees of freedom). The MPEG-I roadmap below points to many technologies that are relevant to our project. One of these technologies is the 3D point cloud that offers a relatively simple and versatile volumetric representation. MPEG plans to release a new standard to code point clouds in 2020. In 2017, MPEG issued a call to invite proposals for the coding of point clouds captured using a wide array of capture devices and objects. After the conclusion of the CFP, MPEG announced two classes of codecs to encode dynamic sequences of point clouds. The first is V-PCC which is a video-based approach that projects point cloud geometry and attributes to 2D and then leverages existing video codecs to encode the point clouds. V-PCC is suitable for dense point clouds and for offline applications as this approach allows the use of hardware acceleration on modern GPUs. The other approach is G-PCC which is a 3D geometry-based approach that decomposes the 3D space to a hierarchical structure to represent point locations. G-PCC is suitable for point clouds with sparse distributions as well as real-time streaming applications such as tele-immersion. This approach also allows for future optimizations based on human perception of volumetric reconstructions

After the recent MPEG meeting 130 in March 2020, new versions of both the codecs have been made available (V-PCC Release 8.0 and G-PCC release 9.0). As the V-PCC standard nears the first public release the focus has been on integrating the codec with the general MPEG-I Metadata for Immersive Video (MIV) distribution format. To this end, the MPEG-I Systems working group is conducting core experiments (CEs), which aim to define metadata that allows to identify and deliver a subset of data currently required by a user. Functionality enabled by such metadata should improve the efficiency of processing and minimize data transmission bandwidth. This metadata will be carried using the MPEG Supplementary Enhancement Information (SEI) stream. During the last two meetings, MPEG has solicited contributions from experts to define the SEI messages for both codecs and different streaming scenarios. For the G-PCC codec, recent developments include the addition of core experiments to determine coding gains offered by incorporating the priors of the sensing system to optimize the coding of lidar acquired point clouds as well as the addition of a new planar mode to reduce the

bitrate of geometry occupancy signalling. Apart from this the group is also soliciting contributions on the definition of new core experiments and point cloud use cases as we approach the release of a public standard.

Figure 50 - MPEG118 version of MP20 Roadmap

5.7. VQEG

The Video Quality Experts Group (VQEG)⁹⁵ provides a forum, via email lists and face-to-face meetings for video quality assessment experts to exchange information and work together on common goals. The general motivation of VQEG is to advance the field of video quality assessment by investigating new and advanced subjective and objective methods for assessing quality. Over the years, VQEG has developed a systematic approach to validation testing which typically includes the collection of several subjective databases whose results are to be predicted by the objective video quality models under examination. An important element of the VQEG approach is the formulation of test plans that clearly and specifically define the procedures for performing objective model validation. These test plans describe the format and range of source content, the scope and nature of degradations that may be applied to the source content, the subjective test methods to be used to collect the subjective data, the test laboratories who perform the subjective assessment tests, the type of objective quality models that may be submitted for the purpose of model validation, the submission procedures of the objective quality models, and finally the statistical techniques and model evaluation metrics to be used. VQEG activities, such as validation tests, are documented in reports and submitted to relevant ITU Study Groups (e.g., ITU-T SG9, ITU-T SG12, ITU-R WP6C), and other SDOs as appropriate. Several VQEG studies have resulted in ITU Recommendations.

The Immersive Media Group (IMG) is a group of VQEG, whose objective is to study the quality assessment of immersive media, including virtual reality, augmented reality, stereoscopic 3DTV and multi-view media. In particular, the goal of the group is to provide guidelines

⁹⁵ VQEG : <https://www.its.bldrdoc.gov/vqeg/vqeg-home.aspx>

regarding subjective methodologies, presentation requirements, and quality of experience metrics for immersive media and virtual reality gaming. That includes both using traditional content that is being repurposed for virtual reality, as well as new content captured specifically for virtual reality, using for example omnidirectional and light field cameras. One of the latest efforts by the IMG is to conduct a cross-lab testing for 360 degree videos, to provide guidelines for future subjective tests for omnidirectional audio-visual contents.

5.8. VRIF

The VR Industry Forum (VRIF)⁹⁶ was established as a non-profit organization during CES 2017, after a year of informal meetings. Its aim is to further the widespread availability of high quality audio-visual VR experiences, for the benefit of consumers.

VR-IF targets immersive experiences that typically require head-mounted devices, understanding that immersive VR content may also be consumed on “2D flat screens” (like tablets, mobile phones, PC screens, TVs) with navigation capabilities.

VR-IF builds on available specifications and standards and recommends selections where needed, provides guidelines that go beyond standardization, supports interoperability tests and demos, and advocates interoperable solutions and standards.

The current version of the guidelines (version 2.1) does provide specifications and profiles for 360 video, including use cases.

Currently VR-IF is working on the next version (v3.0) which will include Social VR guidelines.

5.9. VRARA

The VR/AR Association⁹⁷ is an international organization designed to foster collaboration between innovative companies and people in the VR and AR ecosystem that accelerates growth, fosters research and education, helps develop industry standards, connects member organizations and promotes the services of member companies. The VRARA has set up a lot of chapters, which enables smaller companies and start-ups to join the Association easily.

⁹⁶VRIF: <https://www.vr-if.org/>

⁹⁷VRARA: <https://www.thevrara.com/>

6. CONCLUSION

The present market analysis aims to provide an update on the current state of the VR market, not only by examining financial forecasts, market segments and applications, current use cases and new hardware releases from constructors but also by exploring the potential future for AR/VR in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, key actors and potential partners that may benefit from VRTogether technical solutions are also analysed and an in-depth analysis is provided.

In terms of long-term AR/VR forecast is for the AR/VR market to reach the \$16-18 billion revenue by 2022, according SuperData and IDC forecasts. However, the next two years are forecast to be impacted by COVID-19 related factors (but not limited to) such as lockdowns, supply chain disruptions and recession economic impacts. As a result, a market contraction is expected from previous years, although a quick rebound is also expected.

In fact, both SuperData and IDC maintain their respective long-term forecast with a promising expected market growth for the following years, assuming market restrictions are lifted mid-year. In fact, the spread of the coronavirus is having a positive effect on demand, which expected to ramp up during the following months as a result increasing number of consumers and employees staying indoors due to social and physical distancing measures placed by governments across the world.

A similar trend is expected in terms of AR/VR adoption. For instance, 2020 Shipments are predicted to suffer a 10.5% year-over-year (YoY) decline for 2020 Q1 followed by a harsher 24.1% decline in 2020 Q2. This is exacting a terrible toll, but it could turn out to be a net positive for AR/VR adoption and use. Families and friends catching up and socializing remotely, enterprise users are collaborating within their own organizations and with others, and service providers carrying on business remotely where possible, are a few examples of activities where AR/VR could help. Hence, as a conclusion AR/VR companies are and will be dealing with knock-on effects both, positive and negative.

AR is also growing and can be expected to be a complementary solution to VR in the forthcoming years. Customers seem to endorse portable technologies, like standalone headsets, despite the lack of power inherent to them.

On the other hand, some actors are slowly pulling away from VR. From hardware constructors (Samsung with their VR headsets) to software makers (Google with their Daydream platform), they all seemingly believe that the current state of technology cannot provide a market significant enough to be viable.

In regard of the hardware and components analysis, we can conclude that the market is relentlessly progressing towards more advanced and capable devices that are slowly enabling mass adoption of VR technologies. Nonetheless, hardware adoption is still lagging behind for optimal market development although it is expected to improve drastically in the short term.

Versatility have been one of the core aspects of VRTogether value proposition, which gathers all this information to continuously adapt to market needs and trends, and thus optimize commercial success. Serving this matter, the present document offers valuable and tangible insights regarding how each components of our value preposition would perform in today's context.

In this regard, it is worth noting the fact that VRTogether sits at the forefront of the market in terms of technological capabilities, especially in those hardware and components segments of most relevance to the project, such as point-cloud capture and encoding systems, real-time 4D capture, volumetric data end-to-end transmission and holographic communication systems.

However, despite the technological capabilities of the project it still remains uncertain how this is going to apply into a fast-paced environment such the AR/VR market in terms of predicted time-to-market or even demand and scalability (in terms of sufficient installed base).

Nonetheless, the positive market trend witnessed during the last few years together with the rather unexpected positive shift COVID-19 has generated in the market, provides room for optimism.

Concomitantly, this places VRTogether in a strong and ambitious position, bridging the gap between exploration and exploitation while enables to start mining the market in search of opportunities.

In fact, key for the future design of a robust exploitation strategy is to identify the most relevant market stakeholders, partners and actors who could potentially benefit from VRTogether's technology. To do so, 3 potential end-use cases have been identified: 1) VR conferencing, 2) Social VR for Broadcasters and Operators; and 3) Interactive Simulation. All of these end-use cases can be encompassed within the category of Social VR, aiming to cater both audience, consumers and enterprises.

For each target end-use case, multiple key partners and solutions have been identified. In this regard, several one more highlighting the market potential of the project and the increasingly market interest for solutions of this kind. Last, but not least D5.2 went on to list those standardization bodies which can and on certain occasions do benefit from our work.

Finally, to conclude, at every new inflection in communication and entertainment technologies, many industries and market segments are bringing their existing models with them in their first efforts to adapt to the new medium. Radio, television, Internet, Web and Mobile have all this seen this progression play out and VR and AR will likely follow that model too.

Eventually, the market and the society are progressively advancing towards an AR/VR ecosystem. A progression that has been accelerated by the unprecedented COVID-19 impact at several levels, ranging from economy to business interactions and even social behaviour.

In this new and sudden context, VR Together embraces open-mindedness, a combination of humility and openness, that is a willingness to seek out and engage with different viewpoints in search of gaining market opportunities. This business philosophy may be of critical importance given the change of paradigm: new technology was developed to fit the way the we worked, now COVID-19 has forced us to change the way we worked to fit the new technology.

Hence, we expect the market to embrace AR/VR and discover new ways to communicate, stablish relationships and ways of entertainment. The future of AR/VR is more than promising and VRTogether's happens to be at the right development stage at the right moment, ready to disrupt into the market.

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